

Formal definition of the kernel type system

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The formalisation is defined over a let-normalised version of the Core language of [Cerberus](#). A proof of soundness of type checking is given in a separate document.

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A1 Commentary

In this document, we formalise “kernel CN”, which is essentially ordinary CN with no type and resource inference. In particular, we assume that all universal quantifiers are explicitly instantiated, that all existential quantifiers have explicit witnesses, and all resource manipulations have proof terms with linear/substructural types. However, we do not require proof terms for the logical properties, since by construction all of the entailments fall into the SMT fragment. Since our inference algorithm can be extended to an elaboration algorithm producing a fully-annotated program, kernel CN could serve as an intermediate representation for the CN compiler (which we have formalised elaboration for iterated resource manipulation, though not footprint analysis). Moreover, the lack of inference makes it a simpler language to prove type safety for.

The kernel CN is a calculus in A-normal form, with a bidirectional type system. Since we handle the majority of C, the entire system is very large, and so we only provide commentary on the highlights.

A1.1 Types and Terms

As in the paper, CN programs have both computational and logical terms. Every such term, computational or ghost, has a *base type* β , which are things like unit, booleans, (mathematical) integers, locations, and records of other base types. Each C type τ is mapped to a corresponding base type – for example, $\beta_{\text{int}^*} = \text{pointer}$. Logical terms are variously referred to as *term*, *ptr* (for pointers), *value* (for pointees), *iarg* (for input-arguments), *oarg* (output-arguments, of type record or array of records), and *iguard* (for boolean guards of iterated resources).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{res} &::= \mathbf{emp} \mid \text{term} \mid \text{pred} \mid \text{qpred} \mid \text{res}_1 * \text{res}_2 \mid \exists y:\beta. \text{res}' \mid \mathbf{if term then res}_1 \mathbf{else res}_2 \\ \text{pred} &::= \alpha(\text{ptr}, \text{iargs})(\text{oarg}) \\ \text{qpred} &::= (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\}(\text{oarg}) \\ \text{res_term} &::= \mathbf{emp} \mid \mathbf{term} \mid \text{pred_term} \mid \text{qpred_term} \mid \langle \text{res_term}_1, \text{res_term}_2 \rangle \mid \mathbf{pack}(\text{oarg}, \text{res_term}') \\ &\quad r \mid \mathbf{fold} \text{res_term}:\text{pred} \mid \text{pred_ops} \\ \text{pred_ops} &::= \mathbf{explode}(\text{res_term}) \mid \mathbf{implode}(\text{res_term}, \text{tag}) \mid \mathbf{iterate}(\text{res_term}, \text{int}) \\ &\quad \mathbf{congeal}(\text{res_term}, \text{int}) \mid \mathbf{break}(\text{res_term}, \text{term}) \mid \mathbf{glue}(\text{res_term}) \\ &\quad \mathbf{inj}(\text{res_term}, \text{ptr}, \text{step}, x. \text{iargs}) \mid \mathbf{split}(\text{res_term}, \text{iguard}) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1: Grammar of Resource Terms

In Figure 1, we give the grammar of resource types (i.e., separation logic predicates) and resource terms (the proof terms used by the kernel Core typechecker). The standard resources *res* can be an empty heap \mathbf{emp} , a boolean condition *term*, the separating conjunction $\text{res}_1 * \text{res}_2$, an existential type $\exists y:\beta. \text{res}$, and the disjunction $\mathbf{if term then res}_1 \mathbf{else res}_2$. We use a conditional rather than a traditional disjunction to avoid backtracking during typechecking.

Resource predicates have special syntax to handle the division of their arguments into inputs and outputs. An occurrence of a predicate is written $\alpha(\text{ptr}, \text{iargs})(\text{oarg})$. This is read as the predicate α , applied

to a pointer argument ptr and a list of other input arguments $iargs$. The output argument $oarg$ is highlighted and in a second set of parentheses. Every predicate has exactly one output argument, of type record (with zero or more fields). A $qpred$ represents the iterated separating conjunction of predicate instances; it quantifies over integer indices x satisfying a guard $iguard$, and is with input arguments $iargs$ and output $oarg$. It represents an instance of α beginning at ptr , and repeating every $step$ bytes, for as long as the $iguard$ is true.

Each resource type has introduction and elimination forms – e.g. $res_1 * res_2$ has pairing and pattern matching proof terms. The standard resource types have the expected rules, and predicate types can be introduced by explicitly folding a predicate definition $\text{fold } res_term : pred$, and unfolded via pattern-matching.

In addition, there are resource operations recording the resource-manipulation steps inference uses to successfully type a program. If we suppress the book-keeping of checking that input arguments match, calculating indices, and updating output arguments, most of these operations have simple intuitions. $\text{explode}(res_term)$ and $\text{implode}(res_term, tag)$ are operations on structs and their members; the first takes an $\text{Owned} \langle \text{struct } tag \rangle$ and turns it into a $\text{Owned} \langle \tau_i \rangle$ for each of its members; the second does the inverse. $\text{iterate}(res_term, int)$ and $\text{congeal}(res_term, int)$ function similarly, but for C’s fixed-size arrays, returning a *quantified* $\text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$ instead.

Morally, break has type $qpred \rightarrow qpred * pred$: it extracts a single predicate from a quantified one, and must return the remainder as well because resource terms are linearly typed; glue has type $qpred * pred \rightarrow qpred$: it is the inverse to break ; split has type $qpred * iguard \rightarrow qpred * qpred$: given a quantified predicate of index-guard $iguard'$, and an $iguard$, if $iguard \rightarrow iguard'$ then it splits the given quantified predicate into two disjoint parts (one of index-guard $iguard$ and the other of $iguard' \wedge \neg iguard$); inj has type $pred * ptr * step * iargs \rightarrow qpred$: it turns a predicate $\alpha(ptr', iargs')$ into a quantified predicate, with $iguard = (x = k)$, where $k = (ptr' - ptr) / step$ and $iargs' = k / x(iargs)$. Because our inference algorithm does not support inferring merging arrays, there is no inverse to split of type $qpred * qpred \rightarrow qpred$.

A1.2 Judgements and Example Rules

The contexts for the rules consist of four parts: (1) \mathcal{C} containing the computational variables from the Core program; (2) \mathcal{L} containing purely logical variables mentioned in specifications; (3) Φ , the constraint context, containing a list of (non-quantified) SMT constraints; and (4) \mathcal{R} a *linear* context containing the resources available at that point during type-checking. Assuming a constraint context of only non-quantified constraints is an acceptable simplification, because the elaboration pass can annotate terms with fully-instantiated constraints, whose quantifiers were either supplied by lemmas, annotations or default instantiation.

We focus on the judgements for typing resource terms and memory actions. The judgement $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow res$ should be read as “under a context of computational variables \mathcal{C} , logical variables \mathcal{L} , constraints Φ and resources \mathcal{R} , the resource term res_term synthesises resource type res ” (the highlighting shows the part of the judgement with an *output mode*). The judgement $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res$ reads similarly, replacing ‘synthesises’ with ‘checks against’.

We need both judgements because variables, folding, predicate operations are naturally typed as synthesising rules, whereas constraints, packing existentials, and conditional resources require checking. Furthermore, as we shall see soon, memory actions require a synthesising judgement (to obtain and manipulate the output argument of $\text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$), whereas top-level values (such as typing spines) require checking judgements.

RES_CHK_IF_TRUE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}) \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{res}_1 \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2}$$

EXPL_IS_ACTION_CREATE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{ret} \equiv \Sigma y_p:\text{pointer}. \text{term} \wedge \exists y:\text{record } \text{init}:\text{bool } \text{value}:\beta_\tau. \text{ret}' \\ 2. \text{ret}' \equiv (y_p \xrightarrow{\text{y.init}} y.\text{value}) * y.\text{init} = \text{false} \wedge \text{I} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{create}(pval, \tau) \Rightarrow \text{ret}}$$

EXPL_IS_ACTION_STORE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{term} \xrightarrow{\tau} _ \\ 2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term} = pval_0) \\ 3. \text{ret} \equiv \Sigma _:\text{unit}. (pval_0 \xrightarrow{\text{true}} pval_1) * \text{I} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{store}(_, \tau, pval_0, pval_1, _, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \text{ret}}$$

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{pred} \equiv \alpha(\text{ptr}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i})(\text{oarg}) \\ 2. \alpha \equiv x_p:\text{pointer}, x_i:\beta_i^i, y:\text{record } \text{tag}_j:\beta_j^j \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals} \\ 3. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow [\text{oarg}/y, [\overline{\text{iarg}_i}/x_i^i], \text{ptr}/x_p](\text{res}) \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{fold } \text{res_term}:\text{pred} \Rightarrow \text{pred}}$$

EXPL_IS_ACTION_LOAD

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{term} \xrightarrow{\text{init}} pval_1 \\ 2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow (\text{term} = pval_0) \wedge (\text{init} = \text{true})) \\ 3. \text{ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\beta_\tau. y = pval_1 \wedge (pval_0 \xrightarrow{\text{true}} pval_1) * \text{I} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{load}(\tau, pval_0, _, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \text{ret}}$$

EXPL_IS_ACTION_KILL_STATIC

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{term} \xrightarrow{\tau} _ \\ 2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term} = pval) \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{kill}(\text{static } \tau, pval, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \Sigma _:\text{unit}. \text{I}}$$

Above is one of two rules for checking a conditional resource. Thanks to the ordered disjunction, the rule is simple: if the SMT solver can statically prove term , then check the resource term against the res_1 . The converse (omitted) checks against res_2 if the SMT solver can prove the negation of the condition; if neither is provable, the rules try to synthesise an under-determined conditional resource (the only way this is possible is if res_term is a variable of an SMT-equivalent type).

The rule for folding predicates shown is simplified for presentation (omitting only the type checking of the all the predicate arguments, and the exclusion of the $\text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$ predicate because it cannot be folded). The first line is a simple lookup based on the predicate name of types of the arguments, and the “body” res of the predicate. The second checks res_term against the res with its arguments (supplied by the fold term) substituted in.

The above rules for typing memory actions are also simplified for presentation. Allocating memory (which takes an alignment $pval$ and a C type τ) synthesises a return type ret representing: a newly created pointer (referred to in the type by the name y_p), some omitted constraints about alignment and representability (term), a logical value (y) representing the output argument of a points-to/ $\text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$ resource (which differs slightly from the implementation in that it additionally contains the initialisedness status), the resource itself ($\text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle(y_p)(y)$ is pretty-printed in more familiar \mapsto notation), and a constraint that the points-to is not initialised.

Loading from a memory location requires a correctly typed resource term, *and* its output argument’s initialisedness status init to be true. Because the types are linear, it not only returns the pointed-to value, but also the same permission it consumed.

Storing to a memory location is similar to loading: it requires a points-to permission, but without any constraints on its initialisedness. The permission it returns reflects the fact that the pointee is definitely initialised, and that a new value is pointed to by this location.

De-allocating memory is the converse of allocating memory: a resource term is required, but not returned.

A1.3 Differences from Implementation

There are some minor differences between the implementation and the formalisation. The formalisation has a richer grammar of resources: this means it can support tagged unions more succinctly and can open predicates in more cases. The formalisation assumes that iterated resources output arguments have type array of records, whereas the implementation uses records of arrays.

A2 Types and Patterns

A2.1 Resource Related

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(iguard, iguard') \rightsquigarrow \text{opt_cmp_term}}$
 with ordering and minimum opt_cmp_term

given constraints Φ , $iguard$ is potentially included in $iguard'$ (or vice-versa) with

$$\frac{\text{IG_CMP_EQ} \quad 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \forall x. iguard \leftrightarrow iguard')}{\Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(iguard, iguard') \rightsquigarrow \text{Eq}, iguard}$$

$$\frac{\text{IG_CMP_LT} \quad 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \forall x. iguard \rightarrow iguard')}{\Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(iguard, iguard') \rightsquigarrow \text{Lt}, iguard}$$

$$\frac{\text{IG_CMP_GT} \quad 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \forall x. iguard' \rightarrow iguard)}{\Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(iguard, iguard') \rightsquigarrow \text{Gt}, iguard'}$$

$$\frac{\text{IG_CMP_NONE}}{\Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(iguard, iguard') \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \sqsubseteq? \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \text{opt_cmp}}$
 with ordering opt_cmp

given constraints Φ , $qpred_term$ is potentially included in $qpred_term'$ (or vice-versa)

$$\frac{\text{Q_CMP_NAME_NEQ} \quad 1. \alpha_1 \neq \alpha_2}{\Phi \vdash (-; -)\{\alpha_2(- + - \times -, -)\} \sqsubseteq? (-; -)\{\alpha_1(- + - \times -, -)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}$$

$$\frac{\text{Q_CMP_PTRSTEP_NEQ} \quad \begin{array}{l} 1. \text{term}_1 \equiv (ptr = ptr') \wedge (step = step') \\ 2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \neg \text{term}_1) \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash (x; -)\{\alpha(ptr + x \times step, -)\} \sqsubseteq? (x; -)\{\alpha(ptr' + x \times step', -)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}$$

Q_CMP_IG_NEQ

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{term}_1 \equiv (\text{ptr} = \text{ptr}') \wedge (\text{step} = \text{step}') \\
2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}_1) \\
3. \Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(\text{iguard}, \text{iguard}') \rightsquigarrow \text{None} \\
\hline
\Phi \vdash (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, -)\} \sqsubseteq? (x; \text{iguard}')\{\alpha(\text{ptr}' + x \times \text{step}', -)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}
\end{array}$$

Q_CMP_IARG_NEQ

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{term}_1 \equiv (\text{ptr} = \text{ptr}') \wedge (\text{step} = \text{step}') \\
2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}_1) \\
3. \Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(\text{iguard}, \text{iguard}') \rightsquigarrow \text{cmp}, \text{iguard}'' \\
4. \text{term}_2 \equiv \text{iguard}'' \rightarrow \bigwedge (\overline{\text{iarg}_i = \text{iarg}'_i}) \\
5. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \exists x. \neg \text{term}_2) \\
\hline
\Phi \vdash (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, -)\} \sqsubseteq? (x; \text{iguard}')\{\alpha(\text{ptr}' + x \times \text{step}', -)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}
\end{array}$$

Q_CMP_COMPARABLE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{term}_1 \equiv (\text{ptr} = \text{ptr}') \wedge (\text{step} = \text{step}') \\
2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}_1) \\
3. \Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(\text{iguard}, \text{iguard}') \rightsquigarrow \text{cmp}, \text{iguard}'' \\
4. \text{term}_2 \equiv \text{iguard}'' \rightarrow \bigwedge (\overline{\text{iarg}_i = \text{iarg}'_i}) \\
5. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \forall x. \text{term}_2) \\
\hline
\Phi \vdash (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, -)\} \sqsubseteq? (x; \text{iguard}')\{\alpha(\text{ptr}' + x \times \text{step}', -)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{cmp}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{res_req} \equiv \text{res_req}' \rightsquigarrow \text{bool}}$ resource equality: given constraints Φ , res_req and $\text{res_req}'$ are equal according to bool

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{REQ_EQ_PP_NAME_NEQ} \\
\frac{1. \alpha_1 \neq \alpha_2}{\Phi \vdash \alpha_1(-, -) \equiv \alpha_2(-, -) \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{false}}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{REQ_EQ_PP_IARG_NEQ} \\
\frac{1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \neg(ptr_1 = ptr_2 \wedge \bigwedge(\overline{iarg_1 i} = \overline{iarg_2 i})))}{\Phi \vdash \alpha(ptr_1, \overline{iarg_1 i}^i) \equiv \alpha(ptr_2, \overline{iarg_2 i}^i) \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{false}}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{REQ_EQ_PP_EQ} \\
\frac{1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow ptr_1 = ptr_2 \wedge \bigwedge(\overline{iarg_1 i} = \overline{iarg_2 i}^i))}{\Phi \vdash \alpha(ptr_1, \overline{iarg_1 i}^i) \equiv \alpha(ptr_2, \overline{iarg_2 i}^i) \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{true}}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{REQ_EQ_QQ_EQ} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \sqsubseteq? \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{Eq}}{\Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \equiv \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{true}}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{REQ_EQ_QQ_NEQ} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \sqsubseteq? \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{opt_cmp}}{\Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \equiv \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{false}}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash res \equiv res'}$ resource equality: given constraints Φ , res is equal to res'

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{RES_EQ_EMP} \\
\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \mathbf{emp} \equiv \mathbf{emp}}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{RES_EQ_PHI} \\
\frac{1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term \leftrightarrow term')}{\Phi \vdash term \equiv term'}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{RES_EQ_PRED} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash pred_term \equiv pred_term' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{true}}{\Phi \vdash pred_term(-) \equiv pred_term'(-)}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{RES_EQ_QPRED} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \equiv \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{true}}{\Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term}(-) \equiv \text{qpred_term}'(-)}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{RES_EQ_SEPCONJ} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash res_1 \equiv res'_1 \\ 2. \Phi \vdash res_2 \equiv res'_2}{\Phi \vdash res_1 * res_2 \equiv res'_1 * res'_2}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{RES_EQ_EXISTS} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash res \equiv res'}{\Phi \vdash \exists ident:\beta. res \equiv \exists ident:\beta. res'}
\end{array}$$

RES_EQ_ORDDISJ

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}_1 \leftrightarrow \text{term}_2) \\ 2. \Phi, \text{term}_1 \vdash \text{res}_{11} \equiv \text{res}_{21} \\ 3. \Phi, \neg \text{term}_1 \vdash \text{res}_{21} \equiv \text{res}_{22} \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \text{if } \text{term}_1 \text{ then } \text{res}_{11} \text{ else } \text{res}_{12} \equiv \text{if } \text{term}_2 \text{ then } \text{res}_{21} \text{ else } \text{res}_{22}}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res) \rightsquigarrow res', bool}$ partial-simplification of resources: given constraints Φ , res partially simplifies (strips ifs) to res'

RES_SIMPREC_IF_TRUE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}) \\ 2. \Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res_1) \rightsquigarrow res'_1, bool \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(\text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2) \rightsquigarrow res'_1, \text{true}}$$

RES_SIMPREC_IF_FALSE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \neg \text{term}) \\ 2. \Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res_2) \rightsquigarrow res'_2, bool \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(\text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2) \rightsquigarrow res'_2, \text{true}}$$

RES_SIMPREC_SEPCONJ

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res_1) \rightsquigarrow res'_1, bool_1 \\ 2. \Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res_2) \rightsquigarrow res'_2, bool_2 \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res_1 * res_2) \rightsquigarrow res'_1 * res'_2, bool_1 || bool_2}$$

RES_SIMPREC_EXISTS

$$\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res) \rightsquigarrow res', bool}{\Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(\exists y:\beta. res) \rightsquigarrow \exists y:\beta. res', bool}$$

RES_SIMPREC_NOCHANGE

$$\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res) \rightsquigarrow res, \text{false}}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{simp}(res) \rightsquigarrow opt_res}$ partial-simplification of resources: given constraints Φ , res attempts a partial simplification (strips ifs) to opt_res

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{SIMP_NOSIMP} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res) \rightsquigarrow res, \text{false}}{\Phi \vdash \text{simp}(res) \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{SIMP_SIMP} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(res) \rightsquigarrow res', \text{true}}{\Phi \vdash \text{simp}(res) \rightsquigarrow res'}
\end{array}$$

A2.2 Return Type Equality

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash ret \equiv ret'}$ return type equality: given constraints Φ , ret is equal to ret'

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{RET_EQ_END} \\
\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \mathbf{I} \equiv \mathbf{I}}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{RET_EQ_COMP} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash ret \equiv ret'}{\Phi \vdash \Sigma y:\beta. ret \equiv \Sigma y:\beta. ret'}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{RET_EQ_LOG} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash ret \equiv ret'}{\Phi \vdash \exists y:\beta. ret \equiv \exists y:\beta. ret'}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{RET_EQ_PHI} \\
\frac{1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term \leftrightarrow term')}{\Phi \vdash term \wedge ret \equiv term' \wedge ret'}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{RET_EQ_RES} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash res \equiv res' \\
2. \Phi \vdash ret \equiv ret'}{\Phi \vdash res * ret \equiv res' * ret'}
\end{array}$$

A2.3 Patterns

$\boxed{pat:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C} \text{ with } term}$ computational pattern to context: pat and type β produces context \mathcal{C} and constraint $term$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PAT_COMP_NO_SYM_ANNOT} \quad \text{PAT_COMP_SYM_ANNOT} \quad \text{PAT_COMP_NIL} \\
\hline
\text{.}:\beta:\beta \rightsquigarrow \text{. with } _ \quad \text{x}:\beta:\beta \rightsquigarrow \text{x}:\beta \text{ with } \text{x} \quad \text{Nil } \beta():\text{list } \beta \rightsquigarrow \text{. with nil}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PAT_COMP_CONS} \quad \text{PAT_COMP_TUPLE} \\
\hline
\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{pat}_1:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1 \text{ with } \text{term}_1 \\
2. \text{pat}_2:\text{list } \beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_2 \text{ with } \text{term}_2
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{pat}_i:\beta_i \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_i \text{ with } \text{term}_i \\
\hline
\text{Tuple}(\overline{\text{pat}_i^i}):\overline{\beta_i^i} \rightsquigarrow \overline{\mathcal{C}_i^i} \text{ with } (\overline{\text{term}_i^i})
\end{array} \\
\hline
\text{Cons}(\text{pat}_1, \text{pat}_2):\text{list } \beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2 \text{ with } \text{term}_1 :: \text{term}_2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PAT_COMP_ARRAY} \quad \text{PAT_COMP_SPECIFIED} \\
\hline
\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{pat}_i:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_i \text{ with } \text{term}_i \\
\hline
\text{Array}(\overline{\text{pat}_i^i}):\text{array } \beta \rightsquigarrow \overline{\mathcal{C}_i^i} \text{ with } [\overline{\text{term}_i^i}]
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{pat}:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C} \text{ with } \text{term} \\
\hline
\text{Specified}(\text{pat}):\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C} \text{ with } \text{term}
\end{array}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\text{ident_or_pat}:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C} \text{ with } \text{term}}$ identifier-or-pattern to context: *ident_or_pat* and type β produces context \mathcal{C} and constraint *term*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PAT_SYM_OR_PAT_SYM} \quad \text{PAT_SYM_OR_PAT_PAT} \\
\hline
\text{x}:\beta \rightsquigarrow \text{x}:\beta \text{ with } \text{x} \quad \begin{array}{l}
1. \text{pat}:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C} \text{ with } \text{term} \\
\hline
\text{pat}:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C} \text{ with } \text{term}
\end{array}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}:\text{res} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}$ resources pattern to context: given constraints Φ , *res_pat* of type *res* produces contexts $\mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PAT_RES_MATCH_EMP} \quad \text{PAT_RES_MATCH_PHI} \quad \text{PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_TRUE} \\
\hline
\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{emp}:\text{emp} \rightsquigarrow \text{.; .;} \quad \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{term}:\text{term} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi', \text{term}; \mathcal{R}' \quad \begin{array}{l}
1. \text{smt } (\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}) \\
2. \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}:\text{res}_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \\
\hline
\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}:\text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}
\end{array}
\end{array}$$

PAT_RES_MATCH_IF_FALSE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \neg \text{term}) \\ 2. \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}: \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \end{array}}{\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}: \text{if term then res}_1 \text{ else res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}}$$

PAT_RES_MATCH_VAR

$$\frac{1. (\text{replace res with res_norm for normalised contexts})}{\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash r: \text{res} \rightsquigarrow \cdot; \cdot; r: \text{res}}$$

PAT_RES_MATCH_SEPCONJ

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}_1: \text{res}_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}_1 \\ 2. \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}_2: \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2 \end{array}}{\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \langle \text{res_pat}_1, \text{res_pat}_2 \rangle: \text{res}_1 * \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_1, \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2}$$

PAT_RES_MATCH_PACK

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{L}, x: \beta; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}: x/y(\text{res}) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{pack}(x, \text{res_pat}): \exists y: \beta. \text{res} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}', x: \beta; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}$$

PAT_RES_MATCH_FOLD

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \alpha \neq \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle \\ 2. \alpha \equiv x_p: _, \overline{x_i: _}^i, y: _ \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals} \\ 3. \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}: [\text{oarg}/y, [\overline{iarg_i/x_i}^i], \text{ptr}/x_p](\text{res}) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}' \end{array}}{\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{fold}(\text{res_pat}): \alpha(\text{ptr}, \text{iargs})(\text{oarg}) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}: \text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}$ return pattern to context: given context $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, ret_pat and return type ret produces contexts $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

PAT_RET_EMPTY

$$\frac{}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash :I \rightsquigarrow \cdot; \cdot; \cdot; \cdot}$$

PAT_RET_COMP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{ident_or_pat}: \beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1 \text{ with } \text{term}_1 \\ 2. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}: \text{term}_1/y(\text{ret}) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2 \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{comp ident_or_pat, ret_pat}: \Sigma y: \beta. \text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2}$$

PAT_RET_LOG

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}, x:\beta; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}:x/y(\text{ret}) \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{log } x, \text{ret_pat}:\exists y:\beta. \text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_2; y:\beta, \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2}$$

PAT_RET_PHI

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}:\text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}:\text{term} \wedge \text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi', \text{term}; \mathcal{R}'}$$

PAT_RET_RES

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res_pat}:\text{res} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}_1 \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}:\text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_2 \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{res } \text{res_pat}, \text{ret_pat}:\text{res} * \text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2; \Phi_1, \Phi_2; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}:\text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}$ return pattern to context: given constraints Φ , ret_pat and return type ret produces contexts $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

PAT_RET'_AUX

$$\frac{1. \cdot; \cdot; \Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}:\text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{\Phi \vdash \text{ret_pat}:\text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}$$

A3 Explicit System

A3.1 Pure Expressions

$\boxed{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{object_value} \Rightarrow \beta}$ object value synthesises: given \mathcal{C} , *object_value* synthesises type β

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_OBJ_INT} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{mem_int} \Rightarrow \text{integer} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_OBJ_PTR} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{mem_ptr} \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_OBJ_ARR} \\ \hline 1. \overline{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{object_value}_i \Rightarrow \beta^i} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{array}(\text{specified_object_value}_i) \Rightarrow \text{array } \beta \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_OBJ_STRUCT} \\ \hline 1. \text{struct tag} \ \& \ \overline{\text{member}_i : \tau_i}^i \in \text{Globals} \\ 2. \overline{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{mem_val}_i \Rightarrow \beta_{\tau_i}^i} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash (\text{struct tag})\{\text{member}_i : \tau_i = \text{mem_val}_i\} \Rightarrow \text{struct tag} \end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{pval} \Rightarrow \beta}$ pure value synthesises: given \mathcal{C} , *pval* synthesises type β

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_VAR} \\ \hline 1. x : \beta \in \mathcal{C} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash x \Rightarrow \beta \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_OBJ} \\ \hline 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{object_value} \Rightarrow \beta \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{object_value} \Rightarrow \beta \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_LOADED} \\ \hline 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{object_value} \Rightarrow \beta \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{specified_object_value} \Rightarrow \beta \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_UNIT} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{Unit} \Rightarrow \text{unit} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_TRUE} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{True} \Rightarrow \text{bool} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_FALSE} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{False} \Rightarrow \text{bool} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_LIST} \\ \hline 1. \overline{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{value}_i \Rightarrow \beta^i} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \beta[\overline{\text{value}_i}^i] \Rightarrow \text{list } \beta \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_TUPLE} \\ \hline 1. \overline{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{value}_i \Rightarrow \beta_i^i} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash (\overline{\text{value}_i}^i) \Rightarrow \overline{\beta_i}^i \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \text{PURE_VAL_CTOR_NIL} \\ \hline \mathcal{C} \vdash \text{Nil } \beta() \Rightarrow \text{list } \beta \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_VAL_CTOR_CONS} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \beta \quad 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_2 \Rightarrow \text{list } \beta}{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{Cons}(pval_1, pval_2) \Rightarrow \text{list } \beta}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_VAL_CTOR_TUPLE} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_i \Rightarrow \beta_i}{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{Tuple}(\overline{pval_i^i}) \Rightarrow \overline{\beta_i^i}}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_VAL_CTOR_ARRAY} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_i \Rightarrow \beta}{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{Array}(\overline{pval_i^i}) \Rightarrow \text{array } \beta}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_VAL_CTOR_SPECIFIED} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta}{\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{Specified}(pval) \Rightarrow \beta}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_VAL_STRUCT} \\
\frac{1. \text{struct } tag \ \& \ \overline{member_i:\tau_i^i} \in \text{Globals} \quad 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_i \Rightarrow \beta_{\tau_i}}{\mathcal{C} \vdash (\text{struct } tag)\{.member_i = pval_i^i\} \Rightarrow \text{struct } tag}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pexpr \Rightarrow pure_ret}$ pure expression synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, $pexpr$ synthesises a pure (non-resourceful) return type $pure_ret$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_EXPR_VAL} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pval \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\beta. y = pval \wedge \mathbf{I}}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_EXPR_ARRAY_SHIFT} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \quad 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_2 \Rightarrow \text{integer}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{array_shift}(pval_1, \tau, pval_2) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = pval_1 +_{\text{ptr}} (pval_2 \times \text{size_of}(\tau)) \wedge \mathbf{I}}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{PURE_EXPR_MEMBER_SHIFT} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \quad 2. \text{struct } tag \ \& \ \overline{member_i:\tau_i^i} \in \text{Globals}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{member_shift}(pval, tag, member_j) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = pval +_{\text{ptr}} \text{offset_of}_{tag}(member_j) \wedge \mathbf{I}}
\end{array}$$

PURE_EXPR_NOT

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{bool}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{not}(pval) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \neg pval \wedge \mathbf{I}}$$

PURE_EXPR_ARITH_BINOP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \text{integer} \\ 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_2 \Rightarrow \text{integer} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pval_1 \text{ binop}_{arith} pval_2 \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = (pval_1 \text{ binop}_{arith} pval_2) \wedge \mathbf{I}}$$

PURE_EXPR_REL_BINOP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \text{integer} \\ 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_2 \Rightarrow \text{integer} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pval_1 \text{ binop}_{rel} pval_2 \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = (pval_1 \text{ binop}_{rel} pval_2) \wedge \mathbf{I}}$$

PURE_EXPR_BOOL_BINOP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \text{bool} \\ 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_2 \Rightarrow \text{bool} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pval_1 \text{ binop}_{bool} pval_2 \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = (pval_1 \text{ binop}_{bool} pval_2) \wedge \mathbf{I}}$$

PURE_EXPR_CALL

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{name}:\text{pure_fun} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto t\text{expr} \in \text{Globals} \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \overline{pval_i}^i :: \text{pure_fun} \gg \text{pure_ret} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{name}(\overline{pval_i}^i) \Rightarrow \text{pure_ret}}$$

PURE_EXPR_ASSERT_UNDEF

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{bool} \\ 2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow pval) \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{assert_undef}(pval, UB_name) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{unit}. y = \text{unit} \wedge \mathbf{I}}$$

PURE_EXPR_BOOL_TO_INTEGER

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{bool}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{bool_to_integer}(pval) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = \text{if } pval \text{ then } 1 \text{ else } 0 \wedge \mathbf{I}}$$

PURE_EXPR_WRAP_I

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{integer} \\
2. abbrev_1 \equiv \max_int_\tau - \min_int_\tau + 1 \\
3. abbrev_2 \equiv pval \text{ rem } abbrev_1 \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{wrapI}(\tau, pval) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = \text{if } abbrev_2 \leq \max_int_\tau \text{ then } abbrev_2 \text{ else } abbrev_2 - abbrev_1 \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash tpval \Leftarrow pure_ret}$ pure top-level value checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, $tpval$ checks against $pure_ret$

PURE_TOP_VAL_DONE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta \\
2. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow pval/y(term)) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{done } pval \Leftarrow \Sigma y:\beta. term \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

PURE_TOP_VAL_UNDEF

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{false}) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{undef } UB_name \Leftarrow \Sigma _:_ _ \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

PURE_TOP_VAL_ERROR

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{false}) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{error}(string, pval) \Leftarrow \Sigma _:_ _ \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash tpepr \Leftarrow pure_ret}$ pure top-level expression checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, $tpepr$ checks against $pure_ret$

PURE_TOP_IF

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{bool} \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, pval = \text{true} \vdash tpepr_1 \Leftarrow \Sigma y:\beta. term \wedge \text{I} \\
3. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, pval = \text{false} \vdash tpepr_2 \Leftarrow \Sigma y:\beta. term \wedge \text{I} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{if } pval \text{ then } tpepr_1 \text{ else } tpepr_2 \Leftarrow \Sigma y:\beta. term \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

PURE_TOP_LET

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pexpr \Rightarrow \Sigma y_1:\beta_1. term_1 \wedge \text{I} \\
2. \text{ident_or_pat}:\beta_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1 \text{ with } term \\
3. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term/y_1(term_1) \vdash tpepr \Leftarrow \Sigma y_2:\beta_2. term_2 \wedge \text{I} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{let } \text{ident_or_pat} = pexpr \text{ in } tpepr \Leftarrow \Sigma y_2:\beta_2. term_2 \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

PURE_TOP_LETT

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash tpepr_1 \Leftarrow \Sigma y_1:\beta_1. term_1 \wedge \text{I} \\
2. \text{ident_or_pat}:\beta_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1 \text{ with } term \\
3. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term/y_1(term_1) \vdash tpepr \Leftarrow \Sigma y_2:\beta_2. term_2 \wedge \text{I} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{let } \text{ident_or_pat}:pure_ret = tpepr_1 \text{ in } tpepr_2 \Leftarrow \Sigma y_2:\beta_2. term_2 \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

PURE_TOP_CASE

1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta_1$
 2. $\frac{}{pat_i; \beta_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_i \text{ with } term_i}^i$
 3. $\frac{}{\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_i; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term_i = pval \vdash tpepr_i \Leftarrow \Sigma y_2: \beta_2. term_2 \wedge \mathbf{I}^i}$
-
- $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{case } pval \text{ of } | pat_i \Rightarrow tpepr_i^i \text{ end} \Leftarrow \Sigma y_2: \beta_2. term_2 \wedge \mathbf{I}$

A3.2 Resource Terms

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash pred_ops \Rightarrow res}$ resource (q)predicate operation term synthesis: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $pred_ops$ synthesises resource res

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_ITERATE

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow ptr \mapsto_{\text{array } n \tau}^{init} value$
 2. $oarg[x].init \equiv init[x]$
 3. $oarg[x].value \equiv value[x]$
-
- $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{iterate}(res_term, n) \Rightarrow (* x. 0 \leq x \wedge x \leq n - 1 \Rightarrow ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau) \xrightarrow{oarg[x].init}_{\tau} oarg[x].value)$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_CONGEAL

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow (* x. iguard \Rightarrow ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau) \xrightarrow{oarg[x].init}_{\tau} oarg[x].value)$
 2. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \forall x. iguard \leftrightarrow (0 \leq x \wedge x \leq n - 1))$
 3. $init[x] \equiv oarg[x].init$
 4. $value[x] \equiv oarg[x].value$
-
- $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{congeal}(res_term, n) \Rightarrow ptr \mapsto_{\text{array } n \tau}^{init} value$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_EXPLODE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow ptr \mapsto_{\text{struct tag}}^{init} value \\
2. \text{struct tag} \ \& \ \overline{member_i : \tau_i^i} \in \text{Globals} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{explode}(res_term) \Rightarrow * (ptr +_{\text{ptr}} \text{offset_of}_{tag}(member_i) \xrightarrow{\tau_i}^{init.member_i} value.member_i)
\end{array}$$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_IMPLODE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow * (ptr_i \xrightarrow{\tau_i}^{init_i} value_i) \\
2. \text{struct tag} \ \& \ \overline{member_i : \tau_i^i} \in \text{Globals} \\
3. \overline{init.member_i} \equiv \overline{init_i^i} \\
4. \overline{value.member_i} \equiv \overline{value_i^i} \\
5. ptr \equiv ptr_0 - \text{offset_of}_{tag}(member_0) \\
6. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \bigwedge (ptr = ptr_i - \text{offset_of}_{tag}(member_i)^i)) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{implode}(res_term, tag) \Rightarrow ptr \mapsto_{\text{struct tag}}^{init} value
\end{array}$$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_BREAK

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash term \Rightarrow \text{integer} \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow (x; \text{iguard}) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \} (oarg) \\
3. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term/x(\text{iguard})) \\
4. \text{qpred} \equiv (x; \text{iguard} \wedge (x \neq term)) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \} (oarg) \\
5. \text{pred} \equiv \alpha(ptr + (term \times step), term/x(iargs)) (oarg[term]) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{break}(res_term, term) \Rightarrow \text{qpred} * \text{pred}
\end{array}$$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_GLUE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow (x; \text{iguard}) \{ \alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}_1}^i) \} (\text{oarg}_1) * \alpha(\text{ptr}_2, \overline{\text{iarg}_2}^i) (\text{oarg}_2) \\
2. \text{term} \equiv (\text{ptr}_2 - \text{ptr}_1) / \text{step} \\
3. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \bigwedge ((\overline{\text{term}/x(\text{iarg}_1)}^i) = \overline{\text{iarg}_2}^i)) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{glue}(\text{res_term}) \Rightarrow (x; \text{iguard} \vee x = \text{term}) \{ \alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}_1}^i) \} (\text{oarg}_1[\text{term}] := \text{oarg}_2)
\end{array}$$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_INJ

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \alpha(\text{ptr}_2, \overline{\text{iarg}_2}^i) (\text{oarg}) \\
2. \text{term} \equiv (\text{ptr}_2 - \text{ptr}_1) / \text{step} \\
3. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \bigwedge ((\overline{\text{term}/x(\text{iarg}_1)}^i) = \overline{\text{iarg}_2}^i)) \\
4. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{oarg} \Rightarrow \beta \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{inj}(\text{res_term}, \text{ptr}_1, \text{step}, x, \overline{\text{iarg}_1}^i) \Rightarrow (x; x = \text{term}) \{ \alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}_1}^i) \} ((\text{default array } \beta)[\text{term}] := \text{oarg})
\end{array}$$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS_SPLIT

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow (x; \text{iguard}') \{ \alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs}) \} (\text{oarg}) \\
2. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \forall x. \text{iguard} \rightarrow \text{iguard}') \\
3. \text{iguard}_2 \equiv \text{iguard}' \wedge \neg \text{iguard} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{split}(\text{res_term}, \text{iguard}) \Rightarrow (x; \text{iguard}) \{ \alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs}) \} (\text{oarg}) * (x; \text{iguard}_2) \{ \alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs}) \} (\text{oarg})
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{res}}$ resource term synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, res_term synthesises resource res

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
\text{RES_SYN_EMP} & \text{RES_SYN_VAR} & \text{RES_SYN_VARSIMP} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{emp} \Rightarrow \text{emp} & \frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp}(\text{res}) \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; r:\text{res} \vdash r \Rightarrow \text{res}} & \frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp}(\text{res}) \rightsquigarrow \text{res}'}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; r:\text{res} \vdash r \Rightarrow \text{res}'}
\end{array}$$

RES_SYN_FOLD

RES_SYN_PRED

1. $\text{pred_term}' \equiv \alpha(\text{ptr}', \overline{\text{iarg}'_i})$
 2. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, _:\beta_i^i \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals}$
 3. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{ptr}' \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
 4. $\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{iarg}'_i \Rightarrow \beta_i^i}$
 5. $\Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \equiv \text{pred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \text{true}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; _:\text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}) \vdash \text{pred_term}' \Rightarrow \text{pred_term}(\text{oarg})$$

1. $\text{pred_term} \equiv \alpha(\text{ptr}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i})$
 2. $\alpha \neq \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$
 3. $\alpha \equiv x_p:\text{pointer}, \overline{x_i:\beta_i^i}, y:\text{record } \overline{\text{tag}_j:\beta_j^j} \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals}$
 4. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{ptr} \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
 5. $\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{iarg}_i \Rightarrow \beta_i^i}$
 6. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{oarg} \Rightarrow \text{record } \overline{\text{tag}_j:\beta_j^j}$
 7. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow [\text{oarg}/y, [\overline{\text{iarg}_i/x_i^i}], \text{ptr}/x_p](\text{res})$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{fold } \text{res_term}:\text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}) \Rightarrow \text{pred_term}(\text{oarg})$$

RES_SYN_QPRED

1. $\text{qpred_term}' \equiv (x; \text{iguard}')\{\alpha(\text{ptr}' + x \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}'_i})\}$
 2. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, _:\beta_i^i \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals}$
 3. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{ptr}' \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
 4. $\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{iarg}'_i \Rightarrow \beta_i^i}$
 5. $\Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \equiv \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \text{true}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; _:\text{qpred_term}(\text{oarg}) \vdash \text{qpred_term}' \Rightarrow \text{qpred_term}(\text{oarg})$$

RES_SYN_PREDOPS

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{pred_ops} \Rightarrow \text{res}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{pred_ops} \Rightarrow \text{res}$$

RES_SYN_SEPCONJ

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \text{res_term}_1 \Rightarrow \text{res}_1$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \text{res_term}_2 \Rightarrow \text{res}_2$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \langle \text{res_term}_1, \text{res_term}_2 \rangle \Rightarrow \text{res}_1 * \text{res}_2$$

$$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{res}}$$

resource term checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, res_term checks against resource res

$$\frac{\text{RES_CHK_PHI} \quad 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term})}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{term} \Leftarrow \text{term}}$$

$$\frac{\text{RES_CHK_PACK} \quad \begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{oarg} \Rightarrow \beta \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{oarg}/y(\text{res}) \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{pack}(\text{oarg}, \text{res_term}) \Leftarrow \exists y:\beta. \text{res}}$$

$$\frac{\text{RES_CHK_SEP_CONJ} \quad \begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \text{res_term}_1 \Leftarrow \text{res}_1 \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \text{res_term}_2 \Leftarrow \text{res}_2 \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \langle \text{res_term}_1, \text{res_term}_2 \rangle \Leftarrow \text{res}_1 * \text{res}_2}$$

$$\frac{\text{RES_CHK_IF_TRUE} \quad \begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}) \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{res}_1 \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2}$$

$$\frac{\text{RES_CHK_IF_FALSE} \quad \begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \neg \text{term}) \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{res}_2 \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2}$$

$$\frac{\text{RES_CHK_SWITCH} \quad \begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{res} \\ 2. \Phi \vdash \text{res} \equiv \text{res}' \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Leftarrow \text{res}'}$$

A3.3 Spine Judgement

$$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{spine} :: \text{fun} \gg \text{ret}}$$

function call spine checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, compatible *spine*, *fun* produces an *ret*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{EXPL_SPINE_RET} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash :: \text{ret} \gg \text{ret}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{EXPL_SPINE_COMP} \\
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash spine :: pval/x(fun) \gg \text{ret} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash pval, spine :: \Pi x:\beta. fun \gg \text{ret}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{EXPL_SPINE_LOG} \\
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash oarg \Rightarrow \beta \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash spine :: oarg/x(fun) \gg \text{ret} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash oarg, spine :: \forall x:\beta. fun \gg \text{ret}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{EXPL_SPINE_PHI} \\
1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term) \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash spine :: fun \gg \text{ret} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash spine :: term \supset fun \gg \text{ret}
\end{array}
\qquad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{EXPL_SPINE_RES} \\
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash spine :: fun \gg \text{ret} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash res_term, spine :: res \multimap fun \gg \text{ret}
\end{array}$$

A3.4 Indet. seq. expressions

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash action \Rightarrow \text{ret}}$ memory action synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, *action* synthesises return type *ret*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{EXPL_IS_ACTION_CREATE} \\
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{integer} \\
2. term \equiv \text{representable}(\tau^*, y_p) \wedge \text{alignedI}(pval, y_p) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{create}(pval, \tau) \Rightarrow \Sigma y_p:\text{pointer}. term \wedge (y_p \xrightarrow{\text{const}_\tau \text{false}} \text{default } \beta_\tau) * \text{I}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{EXPL_IS_ACTION_LOAD} \\
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_0 \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow term \xrightarrow{\text{init}}_\tau value \\
3. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow (term = pval_0) \wedge (init = \text{const}_\tau \text{true})) \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{load}(\tau, pval_0, -, res_term) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\beta_\tau. y = value \wedge (pval_0 \xrightarrow{\text{const}_\tau \text{true}} value) * \text{I}
\end{array}$$

EXPL_IS_ACTION_STORE

1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval_0 \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
2. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \beta_\tau$
3. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{representable}(\tau, pval_1))$
4. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{term} \mapsto_\tau -$
5. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term} = pval_0)$

$$\frac{}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{store}(-, \tau, pval_0, pval_1, -, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \Sigma _:\text{unit}. (pval_0 \xrightarrow[\text{const}_\tau \text{true}]{\text{true}} pval_1) * \text{I}}$$

EXPL_IS_ACTION_KILL_STATIC

1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{term} \mapsto_\tau -$
3. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term} = pval)$

$$\frac{}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{kill}(\text{static } \tau, pval, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \Sigma _:\text{unit}. \text{I}}$$

$$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{memop} \Rightarrow \text{ret}} \quad \text{memory operation synthesises: given } \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}, \text{ memop synthesises return type } \text{ret}$$

EXPL_IS_MEMOP_REL_BINOP

1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
2. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval_2 \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$

$$\frac{}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash pval_1 \text{ binop}_{rel} pval_2 \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = (pval_1 \text{ binop}_{rel} pval_2) \wedge \text{I}}$$

EXPL_IS_MEMOP_INTFROMPTR

1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$

$$\frac{}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{intFromPtr}(\tau_1, \tau_2, pval) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = \text{cast_ptr_to_int } pval \wedge \text{I}}$$

EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRFROMINT

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{integer}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{ptrFromInt}(\tau_1, \tau_2, pval) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = \text{cast_int_to_ptr } pval \wedge \text{I}}$$

EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRVALIDFORDEREF

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{res_term} \Rightarrow \text{term} \xrightarrow{\text{init}}_{\tau} \text{value} \\ 3. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow (\text{term} = pval) \wedge (\text{init} = \text{const}_{\tau} \text{true})) \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{ptrValidForDeref}(\tau, pval, \text{res_term}) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{aligned}(\tau, pval) \wedge (pval \xrightarrow{\text{const}_{\tau} \text{true}}_{\tau} \text{value}) * \text{I}}$$

EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRWELLALIGNED

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{pointer}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{ptrWellAligned}(\tau, pval) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{aligned}(\tau, pval) \wedge \text{I}}$$

EXPL_IS_MEMOP_PTRARRAYSHIFT

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \\ 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_2 \Rightarrow \text{integer} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{ptrArrayShift}(pval_1, \tau, pval_2) \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = pval_1 +_{\text{ptr}} (pval_2 \times \text{size_of}(\tau)) \wedge \text{I}}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_expr \Rightarrow ret}$ *indet. seq. expression synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, is_expr synthesises return type ret*

EXPL_IS_TVAL

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash tval \Leftarrow ret}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash tval:ret \Rightarrow ret}$$

EXPL_IS_MEMOP

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash memop \Rightarrow ret}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{memop}(memop) \Rightarrow ret}$$

EXPL_IS_ACTION

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash action \Rightarrow ret}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash action \Rightarrow ret}$$

EXPL_IS_NEG_ACTION

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash action \Rightarrow ret}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{neg } action \Rightarrow ret}$$

A3.5 Sequenced expressions

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_expr \Rightarrow ret}$ seq. expression synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, seq_expr synthesises return type ret

EXPL_SEQ_CCALL	EXPL_SEQ_PROC
$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. ident: fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto texpr \in \text{Globals} \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i}^i :: fun \gg ret \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash ccall(\tau, ident, \overline{spine_elem_i}^i) \Rightarrow ret}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. name: fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto texpr \in \text{Globals} \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \overline{spine_elem_i}^i :: fun \gg ret \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash pcall(name, \overline{spine_elem_i}^i) \Rightarrow ret}$

A3.6 Top-level Expressions

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash tval \Leftarrow ret}$ top-level value checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $tval$ checks against return type ret

EXPL_TOP_VAL_DONE	EXPL_TOP_VAL_UNDEF	EXPL_TOP_VAL_ERROR
$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash ret_terms :: to_fun\ ret \gg \mathbf{I}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash done\langle ret_terms \rangle \Leftarrow ret}$	$\frac{1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{false})}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{undef } UB_name \Leftarrow ret}$	$\frac{1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{false})}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{error}(string, pval) \Leftarrow ret}$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow ret}$ top-level seq. expression checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, seq_texpr checks against return type ret

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_VAL	EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETP
$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash tval \Leftarrow ret}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash tval \Leftarrow ret}$	$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pexpr \Rightarrow \Sigma y: \beta. term \wedge \mathbf{I} \\ 2. ident_or_pat: \beta \rightsquigarrow C_1 \text{ with } term_1 \\ 3. \mathcal{C}, C_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term_1 / y(term); \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{let } ident_or_pat = pexpr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow ret}$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETTP

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash texpr \Leftarrow pure_ret \\
2. ident_or_pat:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1 \text{ with } term_1 \\
3. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term_1/y(term); \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{let } ident_or_pat: pure_ret = texpr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow ret
\end{array}$$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LET

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}' \vdash seq_expr \Rightarrow ret_1 \\
2. \Phi \vdash ret_pat:ret_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}_1 \\
3. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi, \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret_2 \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{let } ret_pat = seq_expr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow ret_2
\end{array}$$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_LETT

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}' \vdash texpr_1 \Leftarrow ret_1 \\
2. \Phi \vdash ret_pat:ret_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}_1 \\
3. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi, \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash texpr_2 \Leftarrow ret_2 \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{let } ret_pat:ret_1 = texpr_1 \text{ in } texpr_2 \Leftarrow ret_2
\end{array}$$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_CASE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta_1 \\
2. \overline{pat_i:\beta_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_i \text{ with } term_i}^i \\
3. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_i; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term_i = pval; \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr_i \Leftarrow ret^i \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{case } pval \text{ of } \overline{pat_i \Rightarrow texpr_i}^i \text{ end} \Leftarrow ret
\end{array}$$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_IF

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{bool} \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, pval = \text{true}; \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr_1 \Leftarrow ret \\
3. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, pval = \text{false}; \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr_2 \Leftarrow ret \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{if } pval \text{ then } texpr_1 \text{ else } texpr_2 \Leftarrow ret
\end{array}$$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_RUN

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. ident:fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto texpr \in \text{Globals} \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \overline{pval_i}^i :: fun \gg \text{false} \wedge \text{I} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{run } ident \overline{pval_i}^i \Leftarrow \text{false} \wedge \text{I}
\end{array}$$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ_BOUND

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow ret \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{bound } [int](is_texpr) \Leftarrow ret
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow ret}$ top-level indet. seq. expression checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, is_texpr checks against return type ret

EXPL_TOP_IS_LETS

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}' \vdash is_expr \Rightarrow ret_1 \\
 2. \Phi \vdash ret_pat:ret_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}_1 \\
 3. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi, \Phi_1; \mathcal{R}, \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret_2 \\
 \hline
 \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}', \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{let strong } ret_pat = is_expr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow ret_2
 \end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret}$ top-level expression checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $texpr$ checks against return type ret

EXPL_TOP_IS

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow ret}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow ret}$$

EXPL_TOP_SEQ

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow ret}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow ret}$$

A4 Elaboration System

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \in? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{opt_term}}$

given constraints Φ , pred_term is potentially a part of qpred_term at index opt_term

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{PINQ_NAME_NEQ} \\
 \frac{1. \alpha_1 \neq \alpha_2}{\Phi \vdash \alpha_1(-, -) \in? (-; -)\{\alpha_2(- + - \times -, -)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}} \\
 \\
 \text{PINQ_IG_OR_IARG_NEQ} \\
 \frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{term} \equiv (\text{ptr}_2 - \text{ptr}_1) / \text{step} \\ 2. \text{term}_1 \equiv \text{term} / x(\text{iguard}) \\ 3. \text{term}_2 \equiv \bigwedge (\overline{iarg_1 i = [\text{term} / x](iarg_2 i)^i}) \\ 4. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \neg (\text{term}_1 \wedge \text{term}_2)) \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \alpha(\text{ptr}_2, \overline{iarg_1 i}^i) \in? (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \overline{iarg_2 i}^i)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{PINQ_COMP} \\
 \frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{term} \equiv (\text{ptr}_2 - \text{ptr}_1) / \text{step} \\ 2. \text{term}_1 \equiv \text{term} / x(\text{iguard}) \\ 3. \text{term}_2 \equiv \bigwedge (\overline{iarg_1 i = [\text{term} / x](iarg_2 i)^i}) \\ 4. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}_1 \wedge \text{term}_2) \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \alpha(\text{ptr}_2, \overline{iarg_1 i}^i) \in? (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \overline{iarg_2 i}^i)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{term}}
 \end{array}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{ident:res} -? \text{res_req} \rightsquigarrow \text{res_diff}}$

the difference between ident:res and requested res_req is res_diff

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{RES_DIFF_IF_NONE} \\
 \frac{}{\Phi \vdash \text{:if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 -? \text{res_req} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}} \\
 \\
 \text{RES_DIFF_PP_NONE} \\
 \frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \equiv \text{pred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \text{false}}{\Phi \vdash \text{:pred_term}'(-) -? \text{pred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}
 \end{array}$$

RES_DIFF_PP_EXACT

$$\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \equiv \text{pred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{true}}{\Phi \vdash r:\text{pred_term}'(\text{oarg}) \text{ -? } \text{pred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{r \text{ and } \text{oarg}}}$$

RES_DIFF_PQ_NONE

$$\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \in? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{None}}{\Phi \vdash \text{.}:\text{qpred_term}(\text{.}) \text{ -? } \text{pred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{None}}$$

RES_DIFF_PQ_REM

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \in? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{term} \\ 2. \text{qpred_term} \equiv (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\} \\ 3. \text{rem} \equiv (x; \text{iguard} \wedge (x \neq \text{term}))\{\alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\}(\text{oarg}) \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash r:\text{qpred_term}(\text{oarg}) \text{ -? } \text{pred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{bind} \langle r_1, r_2 \rangle : \text{rem} * \text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}[\text{term}]) = \mathbf{break} (r, \text{term}) \text{ for } r_2 \ \& \ \text{oarg}[\text{term}] \text{ and } r_1 : \text{rem}}$$

RES_DIFF_QP_NONE

$$\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \in? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{None}}{\Phi \vdash \text{.}:\text{pred_term}(\text{.}) \text{ -? } \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{None}}$$

RES_DIFF_QP_MORE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \in? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{term} \\ 2. \text{qpred_term} \equiv (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\} \\ 3. \mathbf{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \exists x. \text{iguard} \wedge (x \neq \text{term})) \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash r:\text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}) \text{ -? } \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{oarg \text{ and } (x; \text{iguard} \wedge (x \neq \text{term}))\{\alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\}}$$

RES_DIFF_QP_LAST

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \in? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{term} \\ 2. \text{qpred_term} \equiv (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr}_1 + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\} \\ 3. \mathbf{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \forall x. \neg (\text{iguard} \wedge (x \neq \text{term}))) \\ 4. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{oarg} \Rightarrow \beta \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash r:\text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}) \text{ -? } \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{inj} (r, \text{ptr}_1, \text{step}, x. \text{iargs}) \text{ and } (\mathbf{default \ array} \ \beta)[\text{term}] := \text{oarg}}$$

RES_DIFF_QQ_NONE

$$\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term} \sqsubseteq? \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}{\Phi \vdash _:\text{qpred_term}'(-) \text{ -? } \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{None}}$$

RES_DIFF_QQ_EQ

$$\frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term}' \sqsubseteq? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{Eq}}{\Phi \vdash r:\text{qpred_term}(\text{oarg}) \text{ -? } \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow r \text{ and } \text{oarg}}$$

RES_DIFF_QQ_LT

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term}' \sqsubseteq? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{Lt} \\ 2. \text{qpred_term} \equiv (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\} \\ 3. \text{qpred_term}' \equiv (x; \text{iguard}')\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\} \\ 4. \text{rem} \equiv (x; \text{iguard} \wedge \neg \text{iguard}')\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\}(\text{oarg}) \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash r:\text{qpred_term}(\text{oarg}) \text{ -? } \text{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \langle r_1, r_2 \rangle : \text{res} = \text{split } (r, \text{iguard}') \text{ for } r_1 \ \& \ \text{oarg}[k] \text{ and } r_2:\text{rem}}$$

$$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{ident}_1:\underline{\text{res}} \text{ +? } \text{res_term}_2:\text{res_req} \ \& \ \text{oarg}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg}_3} \quad \text{combining } \text{ident}_1:\underline{\text{res}}, \text{res_term}_2:\text{res_req} \ \& \ \text{oarg}_2, \text{ results in } \text{res_term} \ \text{and} \ \text{oarg}_3$$

RES_COMB_PQ

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{pred_term} \in? \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{term} \\ 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{oarg}_1 \Rightarrow \text{record } \overline{\text{tag}_i:\beta_i^i} \\ 3. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{oarg}_2 \Rightarrow \text{array record } \overline{\text{tag}_i:\beta_i^i} \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash r:\text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}_1) \text{ +? } \text{res_term}:\text{qpred_term} \ \& \ \text{oarg}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{glue } (\langle \text{res_term}, r \rangle) \text{ and } \text{oarg}_2[\text{term}] := \text{oarg}_1}$$

$$\boxed{\Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{wf } \text{res_req} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \mathcal{R}'} \quad \Phi; \mathcal{R} \text{ fulfil well-formed request } \text{res_req} \text{ (via } \text{res_bind} \text{) for answer } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg}, \text{ with } \mathcal{R}' \text{ leftover}$$

REQ_REJ

1. $\Phi \vdash r:\underline{res} \text{ -? } res_req \rightsquigarrow \text{None}$
 2. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{wf } res_req \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, r:\underline{res} \vdash \text{wf } res_req \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}, r:\underline{res}$

REQ_ACC_CLEAN

1. $\Phi \vdash r:\underline{res} \text{ -? } res_req \rightsquigarrow res_term \text{ and } oarg$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, r:\underline{res} \vdash \text{wf } res_req \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \cdot \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}$

REQ_ACC_REM

1. $\Phi \vdash r:\underline{res} \text{ -? } res_req \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_pat_1:res_1 = res_term_1 \text{ for } r_1 \text{ \& } oarg \text{ and } r_2:rem$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, r:\underline{res} \vdash \text{wf } res_req \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_pat_1:res_1 = res_term_1, \cdot \text{ for } r_1 \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}, r_2:rem$

REQ_ACC_MORE

1. $\Phi \vdash r:\underline{res} \text{ -? } res_req_1 \rightsquigarrow oarg_1 \text{ and } res_req_2$
 2. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{wf } res_req_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_2 \text{ for } res_term_2 \text{ and } oarg_2 \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$
 3. $\Phi \vdash r:\underline{res} \text{ +? } res_term_2:res_req_2 \ \& \ oarg_2 \rightsquigarrow res_term_3 \text{ and } oarg_3$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, r:\underline{res} \vdash \text{wf } res_req_1 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term_3 \text{ and } oarg_3 \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2$

$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash res_req \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$

$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ (check well-formedness of and then) fulfil request res_req (via

res_bind) for answer res_term and $oarg$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

REQ_WF_PRED

1. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, \overline{-i:\beta_i}^i, y':\text{record tag}_j:\beta_j^j \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals}$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{ptr} \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
 3. $\overline{\mathcal{C}}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{iarg}_i \Rightarrow \overline{\beta_i}^i$
 4. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{wf } \alpha(\text{ptr}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i}^i) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \alpha(\text{ptr}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i}^i) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$

REQ_WF_QPRED

1. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, \overline{-i:\beta_i}^i, y':\text{record tag}_j:\beta_j^j \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals}$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{ptr} \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
 3. $\overline{\mathcal{C}}; \mathcal{L} \vdash \text{iarg}_i \Rightarrow \overline{\beta_i}^i$
 4. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{wf } (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i}^i)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i}^i)\} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$

$\boxed{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{ident} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}}$ under-determined conditional resource request: $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ fulfil request for **if term then res₁ else res₂** with **synthesising ident** and $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

IF_ACC

IF_REJ

1. $\Phi \vdash \text{res} \equiv \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, x:\underline{\text{res}} \vdash \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow x \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
1. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow x \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
-
- $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, x:\underline{\text{res}} \vdash \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow x \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}, x:\underline{\text{res}}$

$\boxed{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } \text{res} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}}$ arbitrary resource and output-arg request: $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ fulfil request for resource **res** and output-arg **y** (via **res_bind**) with **checking res_term** and **oarg**, leaving resources $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$

OARG_EMPTY

$$\frac{}{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc_using emp} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind} \cdot \text{for emp and unit} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}}$$

OARG_RETURN

$$\frac{}{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } \bigwedge (\overline{y.x_i = term_i^i}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind} \cdot \text{for term and } \{ \overline{x_i = term_i^i} \} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}}$$

OARG_ENDIF_TRUE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term}) \\ 2. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } res_1 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \end{array}}{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

OARG_ENDIF_FALSE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow \neg \text{term}) \\ 2. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } res_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \end{array}}{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

OARG_ENDIF_UNDERDET

$$\frac{1. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2 \rightsquigarrow x \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc_using if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind} \cdot \text{for } x \text{ and unit} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

OARG_MIDDLEIF

1. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc_using if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and unit} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 2. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } res_3 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_3 \text{ for } res_term_3 \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$
-
- $$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } (\text{if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2) * res_3 \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind, res_bind_3 \text{ for } \langle res_term, res_term_3 \rangle \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$$

OARG_ASSERT

1. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow term)$
 2. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } res \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
-
- $$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } term * res \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } \langle term, res_term \rangle \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$$

OARG_LETPRED

1. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash pred_term \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_1 \text{ for } res_term_1 \text{ and } oarg' \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 2. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } oarg'/y'(res) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_2 \text{ for } res_term_2 \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$
 3. $res_term \equiv \text{pack}(oarg', \langle res_term_1, res_term_2 \rangle)$
-
- $$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } \exists y': \text{record } \overline{tag_j: \beta_j^j}. pred_term(y') * res \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_1, res_bind_2 \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$$

OARG_LETQPRED

1. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash qpred_term \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_1 \text{ for } res_term_1 \text{ and } oarg' \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 2. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } oarg'/y'(res) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_2 \text{ for } res_term_2 \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$
 3. $res_term \equiv \text{pack}(oarg', \langle res_term_1, res_term_2 \rangle)$
-
- $$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } \exists y': \text{array record } \overline{tag_j: \beta_j^j}. qpred_term(y') * res \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind_1, res_bind_2 \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''$$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash action \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } action': norm_ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$

res_bind) to $action': norm_ret$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ leftover

memory action elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, $action$ elaborates (via

ELAB_IS_ACTION_CREATE

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{create}(pval, \tau) \Rightarrow \underline{\text{ret}}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{create}(pval, \tau) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \cdot \text{ for create}(pval, \tau): \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}}$$

ELAB_IS_ACTION_LOAD

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_0 \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \\ 2. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle(pval_0) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\ 3. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow oarg.init = \text{const}_\tau \text{true}) \\ 4. \underline{\text{ret}} \equiv \Sigma y: \beta_\tau. y = oarg.value \wedge pt * \text{I} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{load}(\tau, pval_0, -, -) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for load}(\tau, pval_0, -, res_term): \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

ELAB_IS_ACTION_STORE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_0 \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \\ 2. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_1 \Rightarrow \beta_\tau \\ 3. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{representable}(\tau, pval_1)) \\ 4. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle(pval_0) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } - \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\ 5. \underline{\text{ret}} \equiv \Sigma _:\text{unit}. (pval_0 \xrightarrow[\tau]{\text{const}_\tau \text{true}} pval_1) * \text{I} \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{store}(-, \tau, pval_0, pval_1, -, -) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for store}(-, \tau, pval_0, pval_1, -, res_term): \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

ELAB_IS_ACTION_KILL_STATIC

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_0 \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \\ 2. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle(pval) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } - \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \end{array}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{kill}(\text{static } \tau, pval, -) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for kill}(\text{static } \tau, pval, res_term): \Sigma _:\text{unit}. \text{I} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

$$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash memop \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } memop': \text{norm_ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

to (via res_bind) to $memop': \text{norm_ret}$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ leftover

memory operation elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, $memop$ elaborates

ELAB_IS_MEMOP_PTRVALIDFORDEREF

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval_0 \Rightarrow \text{pointer} \\
2. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (pval_0) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } res_term \text{ and } oarg \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
3. \text{smt} (\Phi \Rightarrow oarg.init = \text{const}_\tau \text{true}) \\
4. ret \equiv \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{aligned}(\tau, pval_0) \wedge pt' * I \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{ptrValidForDeref}(\tau, pval_0, _) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } \text{ptrValidForDeref}(\tau, pval_0, res_term): ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'
\end{array}$$

ELAB_IS_MEMOP_REST

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash memop \Rightarrow ret \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash memop \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \cdot \text{ for } memop: ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash is_expr \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } (is_expr'): ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$ indet. seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, is_expr elaborates (via res_bind) to $is_expr': ret$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ leftover

ELAB_IS_MEMOP

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash memop \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } memop': ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{memop}(memop) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } (\text{memop}(memop')): ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'
\end{array}$$

ELAB_IS_ACTION

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash action \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } action': ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash action \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } (action'): ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'
\end{array}$$

ELAB_IS_NEG_ACTION

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash action \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } action': ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{neg } action \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } (\text{neg } action'): ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'
\end{array}$$

ELAB_IS_PACK

1. $\alpha \equiv x_p:\text{pointer}, \overline{x_i:\beta_i^i}, y:\text{record tag}_j:\beta_j^j \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals}$
 2. $\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{pval} \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
 3. $\overline{\mathcal{C}} \vdash \text{pval}_i \Rightarrow \beta_i^i$
 4. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } [[\overline{\text{pval}_i/x_i^i}], \text{pval}/x_p](\text{res}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 5. $\text{ret} \equiv \Sigma _:\text{unit}. \alpha(\text{pval}, \overline{\text{pval}_i^i})(\text{oarg}) * \text{I}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{pack } \alpha(\text{pval}, \overline{\text{pval}_i^i}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } (\text{done } \langle \text{Unit}, \text{fold } \text{res_term}:\alpha(\text{pval}, \overline{\text{pval}_i^i})(\text{oarg}) \rangle:\text{ret}):\text{ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$$

ELAB_IS_UNPACK

1. $\alpha \equiv x_p:\text{pointer}, \overline{x_i:\beta_i^i}, y:\text{record tag}_j:\beta_j^j \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals}$
 2. $\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{pval} \Rightarrow \text{pointer}$
 3. $\overline{\mathcal{C}} \vdash \text{pval}_i \Rightarrow \beta_i^i$
 4. $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \alpha(\text{pval}, \overline{\text{pval}_i^i}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 5. $\text{res}' \equiv [\text{oarg}/y, [\overline{\text{iarg}_i/x_i^i}], \text{ptr}/x_p](\text{res})$
 6. $\text{ret} \equiv \Sigma _:\text{unit}. \text{res}' * \text{I}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{unpack } \alpha(\text{pval}, \overline{\text{pval}_i^i}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{fold } (x):\alpha(\text{pval}, \overline{\text{pval}_i^i})(\text{oarg}) = \text{res_term} \text{ for } (\text{done } \langle \text{Unit}, x \rangle:\text{ret}):\text{ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{spine}' \text{ and } \text{norm_ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}}$ spine elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, arguments spine and function type $\underline{\text{fun}}$ elaborate (via res_bind) to spine' and result type norm_ret , with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

ELAB_SPINE_EMPTY

- ELAB_SPINE_EMPTY
1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash \text{pval} \Rightarrow \beta$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \text{pval}/x(\underline{\text{fun}}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{spine}' \text{ and } \text{ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash ::\text{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \cdot \text{ for and } \text{ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{pval}, \text{spine} :: \Pi x:\beta. \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{pval}, \text{spine}' \text{ and } \text{ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$$

ELAB_SPINE_LETPRED

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{pred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}} \text{ for } \underline{\text{res_term}} \text{ and } \underline{\text{oarg}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}'} \text{ for } \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \forall y: \text{record } \underline{\text{tag}_j}; \beta_j^j. \text{pred_term}(y) \multimap \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}}, \underline{\text{res_bind}'} \text{ for } \underline{\text{oarg}}, \underline{\text{res_term}}, \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''
\end{array}$$

ELAB_SPINE_LETQPREL

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{qpred_term} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}} \text{ for } \underline{\text{res_term}} \text{ and } \underline{\text{oarg}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{oarg}/y}(\underline{\text{fun}}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}'} \text{ for } \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}'} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \forall y: \text{array record } \underline{\text{tag}_j}; \beta_j^j. \text{qpred_term}(y) \multimap \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}}, \underline{\text{res_bind}'} \text{ for } \underline{\text{oarg}}, \underline{\text{res_term}}, \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''
\end{array}$$

ELAB_SPINE_MIDDLEIF

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc_using if } \underline{\text{term}} \text{ then } \underline{\text{res}_1} \text{ else } \underline{\text{res}_2} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}} \text{ for } \underline{\text{res_term}} \text{ and } \underline{\text{unit}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}'} \text{ for } \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'' \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \text{if } \underline{\text{term}} \text{ then } \underline{\text{res}_1} \text{ else } \underline{\text{res}_2} \multimap \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}}, \underline{\text{res_bind}'} \text{ for } \underline{\text{res_term}}, \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}''
\end{array}$$

ELAB_SPINE_PHI

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \underline{\text{term}}) \\
2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}} \text{ for } \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{term}} \supset \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}} \text{ for } \underline{\text{spine}'} \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'
\end{array}$$

$$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{seq_expr} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \underline{\text{res_bind}} \text{ for } \underline{\text{seq_expr}'}: \underline{\text{norm_ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$$

elaborates (via $\underline{\text{res_bind}}$) to $\underline{\text{seq_expr}'}: \underline{\text{norm_ret}}$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ leftover

seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, seq_expr

ELAB_SEQ_CCALL

1. $\text{ident}:\underline{\text{fun}} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals}$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \overline{\text{spine_elem}_i}^i \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
- $$\frac{}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{ccall}(\tau, \text{ident}, \text{spine}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{ccall}(\tau, \text{ident}, \overline{\text{spine_elem}_i}^i): \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}}$$

ELAB_SEQ_PROC

1. $\text{name}:\underline{\text{fun}} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals}$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \underline{\text{fun}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \overline{\text{spine_elem}_i}^i \text{ and } \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
- $$\frac{}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{pcall}(\text{name}, \text{spine}) \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{pcall}(\text{name}, \overline{\text{spine_elem}_i}^i): \underline{\text{ret}} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash \text{res} \rightsquigarrow \text{res_pat}}$ resource normalisation by pat-matching: under constraints Φ , res will produce a normalised resourced context if it matches against res_pat

ELAB_RES_PAT_IF_TRUE

- ELAB_RES_PAT_EMPTY ELAB_RES_PAT_PHI
- $$\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \text{emp} \rightsquigarrow \text{emp}} \quad \frac{}{\Phi \vdash \text{term} \rightsquigarrow \text{term}}$$
1. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term})$
 2. $\Phi \vdash \text{res}_1 \rightsquigarrow \text{res_pat}$
- $$\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{res_pat}}$$

ELAB_RES_PAT_IF_FALSE

1. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \neg \text{term})$
 2. $\Phi \vdash \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{res_pat}$
- $$\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{res_pat}}$$

ELAB_RES_PAT_VAR

$$\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \underline{\text{res}} \rightsquigarrow r}$$

ELAB_RES_PAT_SEPCONJ

1. $\Phi \vdash \text{res}_1 \rightsquigarrow \text{res_pat}_1$
 2. $\Phi \vdash \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{res_pat}_2$
- $$\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \text{res}_1 * \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \langle \text{res_pat}_1, \text{res_pat}_2 \rangle}$$

ELAB_RES_PAT_PACK

$$\frac{1. \Phi \vdash x/y(res) \rightsquigarrow res_pat}{\Phi \vdash \exists y:\beta. res \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{pack}(x, res_pat)}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash ret \rightsquigarrow ret_pat}$ return-value normalisation by pattern-matching: under constraints Φ , ret will produce a normalised resourced context if it matches against ret_pat

<p>ELAB_RET_PAT_I</p> $\frac{}{\Phi \vdash \mathbf{I} \rightsquigarrow _}$	<p>ELAB_RET_PAT_RES</p> $\frac{1. \Phi \vdash res \rightsquigarrow res_pat \quad 2. \Phi \vdash ret \rightsquigarrow ret_pat}{\Phi \vdash res * ret \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{res} \ res_pat, ret_pat}$	<p>ELAB_RET_PAT_LOG</p> $\frac{1. \Phi \vdash ret \rightsquigarrow ret_pat}{\Phi \vdash \exists x:\beta. ret \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{log} \ x, ret_pat}$
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$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr}$ top-level indet. seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, is_texpr elaborates to $texpr$

ELAB_TOP_IS_LETS

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash is_expr \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{bind} \ res_bind \text{ for } (is_expr'):\Sigma y:\beta. ret \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \quad 2. \Phi \vdash ret \rightsquigarrow ret_pat \quad 3. \Phi \vdash \mathbf{comp_ident_or_pat}, ret_pat:\Sigma y:\beta. ret \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \quad 4. \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}', \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi, \Phi', \Phi_1; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \vdash texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret}_2 \rightsquigarrow texpr' \quad 5. texpr'' \equiv \mathbf{insert_lets}(res_bind, \mathbf{let} \ \mathbf{strong} \ \mathbf{comp_ident_or_pat} = is_expr' \ \mathbf{in} \ texpr')}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \mathbf{let} \ \mathbf{strong} \ \mathbf{comp_ident_or_pat} = is_expr \ \mathbf{in} \ texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret}_2 \rightsquigarrow texpr''}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash tval \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \mathbf{bind} \ res_bind \text{ for } tval' \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}'}$ top-level value elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, $tval$ elaborates (via res_bind) to $tval'$ with $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ leftover

ELAB_TOP_VAL_DONE

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{ret_terms} :: \text{to_fun } \underline{\text{ret}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{ret_terms}' \text{ and } \mathbb{I} \vdash \underline{\mathcal{R}'}}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{done } \langle \text{ret_terms} \rangle \Leftarrow \underline{\text{ret}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{done } \langle \text{ret_terms}' \rangle \vdash \underline{\mathcal{R}'}}$$

ELAB_TOP_VAL_UNDEF

$$\frac{1. \text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{false})}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{undef } \underline{UB_name} \Leftarrow \underline{\text{ret}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \cdot \text{ for } \text{undef } \underline{UB_name} \vdash \underline{\mathcal{R}}}$$

$\boxed{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \rightsquigarrow \text{res_bind}}$ partial-simplification of resource context: given $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ can partially simplify the resources using res_bind

ELAB_SIMP_CTX_SIMP

$$\text{ELAB_SIMP_CTX_EMPTY} \quad \frac{\Phi; \cdot \rightsquigarrow \cdot}{\Phi; \cdot \rightsquigarrow \cdot} \quad \frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp}(\underline{\text{res}}) \rightsquigarrow \underline{\text{res}}' \\ 2. \Phi \vdash \underline{\text{res}}' \rightsquigarrow \underline{\text{res_pat}} \\ 3. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \rightsquigarrow \underline{\text{res_bind}} \end{array}}{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, x:\underline{\text{res}} \rightsquigarrow \underline{\text{res_bind}}, \underline{\text{res_pat}}:\underline{\text{res}}' = x}$$

ELAB_SIMP_CTX_SKIP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{simp}(\underline{\text{res}}) \rightsquigarrow \text{None} \\ 2. \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \rightsquigarrow \underline{\text{res_bind}} \end{array}}{\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, _:\underline{\text{res}} \rightsquigarrow \underline{\text{res_bind}}}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{seq_texpr} \Leftarrow \underline{\text{ret}} \rightsquigarrow \text{seq_texpr}'}$ top-level seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, seq_texpr checks against $\underline{\text{ret}}$ and elaborates to $\text{seq_texpr}'$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_TVAL

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{tval} \Leftarrow \underline{\text{ret}} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{tval}' \vdash \cdot}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{tval} \Leftarrow \underline{\text{ret}} \rightsquigarrow \text{insert_lets}(\text{res_bind}, \text{tval})}$$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_LETP

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pexpr \Rightarrow \Sigma y:\beta. term \wedge I$
 2. $ident_or_pat:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1 \text{ with } term_1$
 3. $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term_1/y(term); \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr'$
-
- $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{let } ident_or_pat = pexpr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{let } ident_or_pat = pexpr \text{ in } texpr'$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_LETTP

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash tpepr \Leftarrow pure_ret$
 2. $ident_or_pat:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1 \text{ with } term_1$
 3. $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term_1/y(term); \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr'$
-
- $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{let } ident_or_pat: pure_ret = tpepr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{let } ident_or_pat: pure_ret = tpepr \text{ in } texpr'$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_LET

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \vdash seq_expr \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } seq_expr': \Sigma y:\beta. \underline{ret}_1 \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1'$
 2. $\Phi \vdash \underline{ret}_1 \rightsquigarrow ret_pat$
 3. $\Phi \vdash \text{comp } ident_or_pat, ret_pat: \Sigma y:\beta. \underline{ret}_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1''$
 4. $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi, \Phi_1; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1', \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1'', \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret}_2 \rightsquigarrow texpr'$
 5. $seq_texpr'' \equiv \text{insert_lets } (res_bind, \text{let } comp_ident_or_pat, ret_pat = seq_expr' \text{ in } texpr')$
-
- $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_2 \vdash \text{let } comp_ident_or_pat = seq_expr \text{ in } texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret}_2 \rightsquigarrow seq_texpr''$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_LETT

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}' \vdash texpr_1 \Leftarrow \Sigma y:\beta. \underline{ret}_1 \rightsquigarrow texpr_1'$
 2. $\Phi \vdash \underline{ret}_1 \rightsquigarrow ret_pat$
 3. $\Phi \vdash \text{comp } ident_or_pat, ret_pat: \Sigma y:\beta. \underline{ret}_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi_1; \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1$
 4. $\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{L}_1; \Phi, \Phi_1; \underline{\mathcal{R}}, \underline{\mathcal{R}}_1 \vdash texpr_2 \Leftarrow \underline{ret}_2 \rightsquigarrow texpr_2'$
 5. $seq_texpr'' \equiv \text{let } comp_ident_or_pat, ret_pat: \Sigma y:\beta. \underline{ret}_1 = texpr_1' \text{ in } texpr_2'$
-
- $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}', \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{let } comp_ident_or_pat: \Sigma y:\beta. \underline{ret}_1 = texpr_1 \text{ in } texpr_2 \Leftarrow \underline{ret}_2 \rightsquigarrow seq_texpr''$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_CASE

1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta_1$
 2. $pat_i; \beta_1 \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}_i \text{ with } term_i$
 3. $\overline{\Phi, term_i = pval; \mathcal{R} \rightsquigarrow res_bind_i^i}$
 4. $\overline{\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C}_i; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term_i = pval; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{insert_lets}(res_bind_i, texpr_i) \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr_i'^i}$
- $$\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{case } pval \text{ of } | pat_i \Rightarrow texpr_i^i \text{ end} \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{case } pval \text{ of } | pat_i \Rightarrow texpr_i'^i \text{ end}}$$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_IF

1. $\mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \text{bool}$
 2. $\Phi, pval = \text{true}; \mathcal{R} \rightsquigarrow res_bind_1$
 3. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, pval = \text{true}; \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \text{insert_lets}(res_bind_1, texpr_1) \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr_1'$
 4. $\Phi, pval = \text{false}; \mathcal{R}_2 \rightsquigarrow res_bind_2$
 5. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, pval = \text{false}; \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \text{insert_lets}(res_bind_2, texpr_2) \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr_2'$
- $$\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{if } pval \text{ then } texpr_1 \text{ else } texpr_2 \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{if } pval \text{ then } \text{insert_lets}(res_bind_1, texpr_1') \text{ else } \text{insert_lets}(res_bind_2, texpr_2')}$$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_RUN

1. $ident: fun \equiv \overline{x_i^i} \mapsto \overline{texpr} \in \text{Globals}$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \overline{pval_i^i} :: fun \gg \text{false} \wedge \text{I}$
- $$\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash \text{run } ident \overline{pval_i^i} \Leftarrow \text{false} \wedge \text{I} \rightsquigarrow \text{run } ident \overline{pval_i^i}}$$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ_BOUND

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{insert_lets}(res_bind, is_texpr')$
- $$\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \text{bound}[int](is_texpr) \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{insert_lets}(res_bind, \text{bound}[int](is_texpr'))}$$

$\overline{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr'}$ top-level expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $texpr$ checks against \underline{ret} and elaborates to $texpr'$

ELAB_TOP_SEQ

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow seq_texpr'}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow seq_texpr'}$$

ELAB_TOP_IS

$$\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr}$$

A5 Operational Semantics

$\boxed{pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma}$ computational value deconstruction: pat deconstructs $pval$ to produce substitution σ

SUBS_PAT_VALUE_NO_SYM_ANNOT SUBS_PAT_VALUE_SYM_ANNOT SUBS_PAT_VALUE_NIL

$$\frac{}{\lambda _ = pval \rightsquigarrow \cdot} \quad \frac{}{x _ = pval \rightsquigarrow pval/x} \quad \frac{}{Nil \beta() = Nil \beta() \rightsquigarrow \cdot}$$

SUBS_PAT_VALUE_CONS SUBS_PAT_VALUE_TUPLE

$$\frac{1. pat_1 = pval_1 \rightsquigarrow \sigma_1 \quad 2. pat_2 = pval_2 \rightsquigarrow \sigma_2}{Cons(pat_1, pat_2) = Cons(pval_1, pval_2) \rightsquigarrow [\sigma_1, \sigma_2]} \quad \frac{1. \overline{pat_i = pval_i \rightsquigarrow \sigma_i^i}}{Tuple(\overline{pat_i^i}) = Tuple(\overline{pval_i^i}) \rightsquigarrow [\overline{\sigma_i^i}]}$$

SUBS_PAT_VALUE_ARRAY SUBS_PAT_VALUE_SPECIFIED

$$\frac{1. \overline{pat_i = pval_i \rightsquigarrow \sigma_i^i}}{Array(\overline{pat_i^i}) = Array(\overline{pval_i^i}) \rightsquigarrow [\overline{\sigma_i^i}]} \quad \frac{1. pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma}{Specified(pat) = Specified(pval) \rightsquigarrow \sigma}$$

$\boxed{ident_or_pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma}$ computational value deconstruction: $ident_or_pat$ deconstructs $pval$ to produce substitution σ

SUBS_PAT_VALUE'_SYM SUBS_PAT_VALUE'_PAT

$$\frac{}{x = pval \rightsquigarrow pval/x} \quad \frac{1. pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma}{pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma}$$

$\boxed{\langle h; res_pat = res_val \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle}$ resource term deconstruction: res_pat deconstructs res_val to produce substitution σ

SUBS_PAT_RES_EMP

$$\overline{\langle h; \mathbf{emp} = \mathbf{emp} \rangle} \rightsquigarrow \langle h; \cdot \rangle$$

SUBS_PAT_RES_PHI

$$\overline{\langle h; \mathbf{term} = \mathbf{term} \rangle} \rightsquigarrow \langle h; \cdot \rangle$$

SUBS_PAT_RES_VAR

$$\overline{\langle h; \mathit{ident} = \mathit{res_val} \rangle} \rightsquigarrow \langle h; \mathit{res_val}/\mathit{ident} \rangle$$

SUBS_PAT_RES_PAIR

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \langle h; \mathit{res_pat}_1 = \mathit{res_val}_1 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h_1; \sigma_1 \rangle \\ 2. \langle h; \mathit{res_pat}_2 = \mathit{res_val}_2 \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h_2; \sigma_2 \rangle \end{array}}{\langle h; \langle \mathit{res_pat}_1, \mathit{res_pat}_2 \rangle = \langle \mathit{res_val}_1, \mathit{res_val}_2 \rangle \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h_2; [\sigma_1, \sigma_2] \rangle}$$

SUBS_PAT_RES_PACK

$$\frac{1. \langle h; \mathit{res_pat} = \mathit{res_val} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle}{\langle h; \mathbf{pack}(\mathit{ident}, \mathit{res_pat}) = \mathbf{pack}(\mathit{oarg}, \mathit{res_val}) \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; [\mathit{oarg}/\mathit{ident}, \sigma] \rangle}$$

SUBS_PAT_RES_FOLD

$$\frac{1. \langle h + h'; \mathit{res_pat} = \mathit{def} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h''; \sigma \rangle}{\langle h + \{\mathit{pred_term}(\mathit{oarg}) \ \& \ \mathit{def} \ \& \ h'\}; \mathbf{fold}(\mathit{res_pat}) = \mathit{pred_term} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h''; \sigma \rangle}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; \overline{\mathit{ret_pat}_i = \mathit{ret_term}_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle}$$

return value deconstruction: $\mathit{ret_pat}_i$ deconstructs $\mathit{ret_val}_i$ to produce substitution σ

SUBS_PAT_RET_COMP

SUBS_PAT_RET_EMPTY

$$\overline{\langle h; \cdot \rangle} \rightsquigarrow \langle h; \cdot \rangle$$

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \mathit{ident_or_pat} = \mathit{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma \\ 2. \langle h; \overline{\mathit{ret_pat}_i = \mathit{ret_term}_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \psi \rangle \end{array}}{\langle h; \mathbf{comp} \mathit{ident_or_pat} = \mathit{pval}, \overline{\mathit{ret_pat}_i = \mathit{ret_term}_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle \sigma(h'); [\sigma, \psi] \rangle}$$

SUBS_PAT_RET_LOG

$$\frac{1. \langle h; \overline{\mathit{ret}_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle}{\langle h; \mathbf{log} \mathit{y} = \mathit{oarg}, \overline{\mathit{ret}_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle \mathit{oarg}/\mathit{y}(h'); [\mathit{oarg}/\mathit{y}, \sigma] \rangle}$$

SUBS_PAT_RET_RES

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_1; res_val \rangle \\
2. \langle h; res_pat = res_val \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h_2; \sigma \rangle \\
3. \langle h_2; \overline{ret_pat_i = ret_term_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h_3; \psi \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; \mathbf{res} \ res_pat = res_term, \overline{ret_pat_i = ret_term_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h_3; [\sigma, \psi] \rangle
\end{array}$$

$\langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: fun \gg \langle h'; \sigma; ret \rangle$ function call spine: heap h and formal parameters x_i assigned to $spine_elem_i$ for function of type fun , produce new heap h' substitution σ and result type ret

SUBS_SPINE_EMPTY

$$\overline{\langle h; \rangle :: ret \gg \langle h; \cdot; ret \rangle}$$

SUBS_SPINE_COMP

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: pval/x(fun) \gg \langle h'; \sigma; ret \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; x = pval, \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: \Pi x:\beta. fun \gg \langle h'; [pval/x, \sigma]; ret \rangle
\end{array}$$

SUBS_SPINE_LOG

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: oarg/x(fun) \gg \langle h'; \sigma; ret \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; x = oarg, \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: \forall x:\beta. fun \gg \langle h'; [pval/x, \sigma]; ret \rangle
\end{array}$$

SUBS_SPINE_RES

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle \\
2. \langle h'; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: fun \gg \langle h''; \sigma; ret \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; x = res_term, \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: res * fun \gg \langle h''; [res_val/x, \sigma]; ret \rangle
\end{array}$$

SUBS_SPINE_PHI

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: fun \gg \langle h'; \sigma; ret \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: term \supset fun \gg \langle h'; \sigma; ret \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\langle pexpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle texpr: pure_ret \rangle$$

PE_TP_ARRAY_SHIFT

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{mem_ptr}' \equiv \text{mem_ptr} +_{\text{ptr}} (\text{mem_int} \times \text{size.of}(\tau)) \\ 2. \text{pure_ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = \text{mem_ptr} +_{\text{ptr}} (\text{mem_int} \times \text{size.of}(\tau)) \wedge \mathbf{I} \end{array}}{\langle \text{array_shift} (\text{mem_ptr}, \tau, \text{mem_int}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done mem_ptr}':\text{pure_ret} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_MEMBER_SHIFT

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{mem_ptr}' \equiv \text{mem_ptr} +_{\text{ptr}} \text{offset.of}_{\text{tag}}(\text{member}) \\ 2. \text{pure_ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = \text{mem_ptr} +_{\text{ptr}} \text{offset.of}_{\text{tag}}(\text{member}) \wedge \mathbf{I} \end{array}}{\langle \text{member_shift} (\text{mem_ptr}, \text{tag}, \text{member}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done mem_ptr}':\text{pure_ret} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_NOT_TRUE

$$\frac{}{\langle \text{not} (\text{True}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done False}:\Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \neg \text{True} \wedge \mathbf{I} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_NOT_FALSE

$$\frac{}{\langle \text{not} (\text{False}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done True}:\Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \neg \text{False} \wedge \mathbf{I} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_ARITH_BINOP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{mem_int} \equiv \text{mem_int}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{arith}} \text{mem_int}_2 \\ 2. \text{pure_ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = \text{mem_int}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{arith}} \text{mem_int}_2 \wedge \mathbf{I} \end{array}}{\langle \text{mem_int}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{arith}} \text{mem_int}_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done mem_int}:\text{pure_ret} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_REL_BINOP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{bool_value} \equiv \text{mem_int}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{rel}} \text{mem_int}_2 \\ 2. \text{pure_ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{mem_int}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{rel}} \text{mem_int}_2 \wedge \mathbf{I} \end{array}}{\langle \text{mem_int}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{rel}} \text{mem_int}_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done bool_value}:\text{pure_ret} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_BOOL_BINOP

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{bool_value} \equiv \text{bool_value}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{bool}} \text{bool_value}_2 \\ 2. \text{pure_ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{bool_value}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{bool}} \text{bool_value}_2 \wedge \mathbf{I} \end{array}}{\langle \text{bool_value}_1 \text{binop}_{\text{bool}} \text{bool_value}_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done bool_value}:\text{pure_ret} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_ASSERT_UNDEF

$$\frac{}{\langle \text{assert_undef} (\text{True}, \text{UB_name}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done Unit}:\Sigma _:\text{unit}. \mathbf{I} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_BOOL_TO_INTEGER_TRUE

$$\frac{}{\langle \text{bool_to_integer} (\text{True}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done } 1:\Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = 1 \wedge \mathbf{I} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_BOOL_TO_INTEGER_FALSE

$$\overline{\langle \text{bool_to_integer}(\text{False}) \rangle} \longrightarrow \langle \text{done } 0 : \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = 0 \wedge \text{I} \rangle$$

PE_TP_WRAP_I

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{abbrev}_1 \equiv \text{max_int}_\tau - \text{min_int}_\tau + 1 \\ 2. \text{abbrev}_2 \equiv \text{pval} \text{ rem } \text{abbrev}_1 \\ 3. \text{mem_int}' \equiv \text{if } \text{abbrev}_2 \leq \text{max_int}_\tau \text{ then } \text{abbrev}_2 \text{ else } \text{abbrev}_2 - \text{abbrev}_1 \\ 4. \text{pure_ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = \text{mem_int}' \wedge \text{I} \end{array}}{\langle \text{wrapI}(\tau, \text{mem_int}') \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{done mem_int}' : \text{pure_ret} \rangle}$$

PE_TP_CALL

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{name} : \text{pure_fun} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals} \\ 2. \langle \cdot ; \overline{x_i = \text{pval}_i}^i \rangle :: \text{pure_fun} \gg \langle \cdot ; \sigma ; \text{pure_ret} \rangle \end{array}}{\langle \text{name}(\overline{\text{pval}_i}^i) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \sigma(\text{texpr}) : \text{pure_ret} \rangle}$$

$$\boxed{\langle \text{texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{texpr}' \rangle}$$

TP_TP_CASE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{pat}_j = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma_j \\ 2. \forall i < j. \text{not}(\text{pat}_i = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma_i) \end{array}}{\langle \text{case pval of } \overline{\text{pat}_i \Rightarrow \text{texpr}_i}^i \text{ end} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \sigma_j(\text{texpr}_j) \rangle}$$

TP_TP_LET_SUB

$$\frac{1. \text{ident_or_pat} = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma}{\langle \text{let ident_or_pat} = \text{pval} \text{ in } \text{texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \sigma(\text{texpr}) \rangle}$$

TP_TP_LET_LET

$$\frac{1. \langle \text{pexpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{tpval} : \text{pure_ret} \rangle}{\langle \text{let ident_or_pat} = \text{pexpr} \text{ in } \text{texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{let ident_or_pat} : \text{pure_ret} = \text{tpval} \text{ in } \text{texpr} \rangle}$$

TP_TP_LET_LETT

$$\frac{1. \langle \text{pexpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{texpr}_1 : \text{pure_ret} \rangle}{\langle \text{let ident_or_pat} = \text{pexpr} \text{ in } \text{texpr}_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{let ident_or_pat} : \text{pure_ret} = \text{texpr}_1 \text{ in } \text{texpr}_2 \rangle}$$

TP_TP_LET_SUB

$$\frac{1. \text{ident_or_pat} = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma}{\langle \text{let ident_or_pat: pure_ret} = \text{done pval in texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \sigma(\text{texpr}) \rangle}$$

TP_TP_LET_LETT

$$\frac{1. \langle \text{texpr}_1 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{texpr}'_1 \rangle}{\langle \text{let ident_or_pat: pure_ret} = \text{texpr}_1 \text{ in texpr}_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{let ident_or_pat: pure_ret} = \text{texpr}'_1 \text{ in texpr}_2 \rangle}$$

TP_TP_IF_TRUE

TP_TP_IF_FALSE

$$\frac{}{\langle \text{if True then texpr}_1 \text{ else texpr}_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{texpr}_1 \rangle} \quad \frac{}{\langle \text{if False then texpr}_1 \text{ else texpr}_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{texpr}_2 \rangle}$$

$\langle h; \text{pred_ops} \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; \text{res_val} \rangle$ big-step resource (q)points-to operation reduction: $\langle h; \text{pred_ops} \rangle$ reduces to $\langle h'; \text{res_val} \rangle$

PREDOPS_RESV_ITERATE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \langle h; \text{res_term} \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{\text{pred_term}(\text{oarg}) \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{pred_term} \rangle \\ 2. \text{pred_term} \equiv \text{Owned} \langle \text{array } n \ \tau \rangle(\text{ptr}) \\ 3. \text{qpred_term} \equiv (x; 0 \leq x \wedge x \leq n - 1) \{ \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau)) \} \\ 4. \text{oarg}'[x].\text{init} \equiv \text{oarg}.\text{init}[x] \\ 5. \text{oarg}'[x].\text{value} \equiv \text{oarg}.\text{value}[x] \end{array}}{\langle h; \text{iterate}(\text{res_term}, n) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{\text{qpred_term}(\text{oarg}') \ \& \ \cdot\}; \text{qpred_term} \rangle}$$

PREDOPS_RESV_CONGEAL

1. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term(oarg) \& \cdot\}; qpred_term \rangle$
 2. $qpred_term \equiv (x; iguard)\{\text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau))\}$
 3. $\text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow \forall x. iguard \leftrightarrow (0 \leq x \wedge x \leq n - 1))$
 4. $pred_term \equiv \text{Owned} \langle \text{array } n \tau \rangle (ptr)$
 5. $oarg'.init[x] \equiv oarg[x].init$
 6. $oarg'.value[x] \equiv oarg[x].value$
-
- $\langle h; \text{congeal}(res_term, n) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pred_term(oarg') \& \text{None}\}; pred_term \rangle$

PREDOPS_RESV_EXPLODE

1. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pred \& \text{None}\}; pred_term \rangle$
 2. $pred \equiv \text{Owned} \langle \text{struct } tag \rangle (ptr)(oarg)$
 3. $\text{struct } tag \& \overline{member_i : \tau_i}^i \in \text{Globals}$
 4. $ptr_i \equiv ptr + \text{offset_of_tag}(member_i)$
 5. $pred_i \equiv \text{Owned} \langle \tau_i \rangle (ptr_i)(oarg_i)$
 6. $oarg_i.init \equiv oarg.init.member_i$
 7. $oarg_i.value \equiv oarg.value.member_i$
-
- $\langle h; \text{explode}(res_term) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \overline{\{pred_i \& \text{None}\}}^i; \langle \overline{pred_term_i}^i \rangle \rangle$

PREDOPS_RESV_IMPLODE

1. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \overline{\{pred_term_i(oarg_i) \& None\}^i}; \langle \overline{pred_term_i}^i \rangle \rangle$
 2. $\mathbf{struct\ tag} \& \overline{member_i:\tau_i}^i \in \mathbf{Globals}$
 3. $pred_term_i \equiv \mathbf{Owned} \langle \tau_i \rangle (ptr_i)$
 4. $ptr \equiv ptr_0 - \mathbf{offset_of}_{tag}(member_0)$
 5. $\mathbf{smt} (\cdot \Rightarrow \bigwedge (\overline{ptr = ptr_i - \mathbf{offset_of}_{tag}(member_i)}^i))$
 6. $pred_term \equiv \mathbf{Owned} \langle \mathbf{struct\ tag} \rangle (ptr)$
 7. $oarg.init.member_i \equiv oarg_i.init$
 8. $oarg.value.member_i \equiv oarg_i.value$
-
- $\langle h; \mathbf{implode}(res_term, tag) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pred_term(oarg) \& None\}; pred_term \rangle$

PREDOPS_RESV_BREAK

1. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\}; qpred_term \rangle$
 2. $qpred_term \equiv (x; iguard) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \}$
 3. $\mathbf{smt} (\cdot \Rightarrow term/x(iguard))$
 4. $ptr' \equiv ptr +_{ptr} (term \times step)$
 5. $qpred_term' \equiv (x; iguard \wedge (x \neq term)) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \}$
 6. $pred_term \equiv \alpha(ptr', term/x(iargs))$
-
- $\langle h; \mathbf{break}(res_term, term) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term'(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\} + \{pred_term(oarg[term]) \& arr_def_heap[term]\}; \langle qpred_term', pred_term \rangle \rangle$

PREDOPS_RESV_GLUE

1. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\} + \{pred_term(oarg') \& opt_def_heap\}; \langle qpred_term, pred_term \rangle \rangle$
 2. $qpred_term \equiv (x; iguard) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, \overline{iarg_i}^i) \}$
 3. $pred_term \equiv \alpha(ptr', \overline{iarg_i}^i)$
 4. $term \equiv (ptr' - ptr) / \mathbf{size_of}(\tau)$
 5. $\mathbf{smt} (\cdot \Rightarrow \bigwedge (\overline{term/x(iarg_i) = \overline{iarg_i}^i}))$
 6. $qpred_term \equiv (x; iguard \vee x = term) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \}$
-
- $\langle h; \mathbf{glue}(res_term) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term(oarg[term] := oarg') \& arr_def_heap[term] := opt_def_heap\}; qpred_term \rangle$

PREDOPS_RESV_INJ

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pred_term(oarg) \& opt_def_heap\}; pred_term \rangle \\
2. pred_term \equiv \alpha(ptr_2, \overline{iarg_2}_i^i) \\
3. term \equiv (ptr_2 - ptr_1) / step \\
4. smt(\cdot \Rightarrow \bigwedge (\overline{term/x(iarg_1)_i} = \overline{iarg_2}_i^i)) \\
5. qpred_term \equiv (x; x = term) \{ \alpha(ptr_1 + x \times step, \overline{iarg_1}_i^i) \} \\
6. \cdot; \cdot \vdash oarg \Rightarrow \beta \\
7. oarg' \equiv (default \beta)[term] := oarg \\
\hline
\langle h; inj(res_term, ptr_1, step, x. \overline{iarg_1}_i^i) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term(oarg') \& \cdot[term] := opt_def_heap\}; qpred_term \rangle
\end{array}$$

PREDOPS_RESV_SPLIT

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\}; qpred_term \rangle \\
2. qpred_term \equiv (x; iguard') \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \} \\
3. smt(\cdot \Rightarrow \forall x. iguard \rightarrow iguard') \\
4. qpred_term_1 \equiv (x; iguard) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \} \\
5. qpred_term_2 \equiv (x; iguard' \wedge \neg iguard) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \} \\
\hline
\langle h; split(res_term, iguard) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{qpred_term_1(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\} + \{qpred_term_2(oarg) \& arr_def_heap\}; \langle qpred_term_1, qpred_term_2 \rangle \rangle
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\text{footprint_of } res_val \text{ in } h \rightsquigarrow h_1 \text{ rem } h_2}$ footprint of *res_val* in heap *h* is *h*₁ with *h*₂ remainder/frame

FOOTPRINT_EMP

FOOTPRINT_TERM

$$\frac{}{\text{footprint_of emp in } h \rightsquigarrow \cdot \text{ rem } h} \quad \frac{}{\text{footprint_of term in } h \rightsquigarrow \cdot \text{ rem } h}$$

FOOTPRINT_PRED

$$\frac{}{\text{footprint_of } pred_term \text{ in } h + \{pred_term(oarg) \& opt_def_heap\} \rightsquigarrow \{pred_term(oarg) \& opt_def_heap\} \text{ rem } h}$$

$$\overline{\text{footprint_of } qpred_term \text{ in } h + \{qpred_term(oarg) \ \& \ arr_def_heap\} \rightsquigarrow \{qpred_term(oarg) \ \& \ arr_def_heap\} \text{ rem } h}$$

FOOTPRINT_SEPPAIR

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{footprint_of } res_val_1 \text{ in } h \rightsquigarrow h_1 \text{ rem } h' \\ 2. \text{footprint_of } res_val_2 \text{ in } h' \rightsquigarrow h_2 \text{ rem } h'' \end{array}}{\text{footprint_of } \langle res_val_1, res_val_2 \rangle \text{ in } h \rightsquigarrow h_1 + h_2 \text{ rem } h''}$$

FOOTPRINT_PACK

$$\frac{1. \text{footprint_of } res_val \text{ in } h \rightsquigarrow h' \text{ rem } h''}{\text{footprint_of } pack(oarg, res_val) \text{ in } h \rightsquigarrow h' \text{ rem } h''}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle}$$

 big-step resource term reduction: $\langle h; res_term \rangle$ reduces to $\langle h'; res_val \rangle$

REST_RESV_VAL

$$\overline{\langle h; res_val \rangle \Downarrow \langle h; res_val \rangle}$$

REST_RESV_SEPPAIR

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \langle h; res_term_1 \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_1; res_val_1 \rangle \\ 2. \langle h_1; res_term_2 \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_2; res_val_2 \rangle \end{array}}{\langle h; \langle res_term_1, res_term_2 \rangle \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_2; \langle res_val_1, res_val_2 \rangle \rangle}$$

REST_RESV_PREDOPS

$$\frac{1. \langle h; pred_ops \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle}{\langle h; pred_ops \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle}$$

REST_RESV_FOLD

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_1; def \rangle \\ 2. \text{footprint_of } def \text{ in } h_1 \rightsquigarrow h_2 \text{ rem } h_3 \end{array}}{\langle h; fold \ res_term:pred_term(oarg) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h_3 + \{pred_term(oarg) \ \& \ def \ \& \ h_2\}; pred_term \rangle}$$

REST_RESV_PACK

$$\frac{1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; res_val \rangle}{\langle h; pack(oarg, res_term) \rangle \Downarrow \langle h'; pack(oarg, res_val) \rangle}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; action \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; is_expr \rangle}$$

ACTION_IS_CREATE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{fresh}(mem_ptr) \\
2. \text{representable}(\tau^*, mem_ptr) \wedge \text{alignedI}(mem_int, mem_ptr) \\
3. pt \equiv mem_ptr \stackrel{\text{const}_\tau \text{false}}{\mapsto_\tau} \text{default } \beta_\tau \\
4. ret \equiv \Sigma y_p:\text{pointer}. term \wedge (y_p \stackrel{\text{const}_\tau \text{false}}{\mapsto_\tau} \text{default } \beta_\tau) * I \\
5. term \equiv \text{representable}(\tau^*, y_p) \wedge \text{alignedI}(mem_int, y_p) \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{create}(mem_int, \tau) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{done} \langle mem_ptr, \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \rangle : ret \rangle
\end{array}$$

ACTION_IS_LOAD

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (term) \rangle \\
2. pt \equiv term \stackrel{\text{init}}{\mapsto_\tau} pval \\
3. \text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow term = mem_ptr \wedge \text{init} = \text{const}_\tau \text{true}) \\
4. ret \equiv \Sigma y:\beta_\tau. y = pval \wedge (mem_ptr \stackrel{\text{const}_\tau \text{true}}{\mapsto_\tau} pval) * I \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{load}(\tau, mem_ptr, _, res_term) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{done} \langle pval, \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \rangle : ret \rangle
\end{array}$$

ACTION_IS_STORE

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (term) \rangle \\
2. pt \equiv term \mapsto_\tau _ \\
3. \text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow term = mem_ptr) \\
4. \text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow \text{representable}(\tau, pval)) \\
5. pt' \equiv mem_ptr \stackrel{\text{const}_\tau \text{true}}{\mapsto_\tau} pval \\
6. ret \equiv \Sigma _:\text{unit}. (mem_ptr \stackrel{\text{const}_\tau \text{true}}{\mapsto_\tau} pval) * I \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{store}(_, \tau, mem_ptr, pval, _, res_term) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h' + \{pt' \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{done} \langle \text{Unit}, \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \rangle : ret \rangle
\end{array}$$

ACTION_IS_KILL_STATIC

1. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (term) \rangle$
2. $pt \equiv term \mapsto_{\tau} -$
3. $\text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow term = mem_ptr)$
4. $ret \equiv \Sigma _:\text{unit}. \mathbf{I}$

$$\frac{}{\langle h; \text{kill}(\text{static } \tau, mem_ptr, res_term) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{done } \langle \text{Unit} \rangle : ret \rangle}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; memop \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; is_expr \rangle}$$

MEMOP_IS_REL_BINOP

1. $bool_value \equiv mem_int_1 \text{ binop}_{rel} mem_int_2$
2. $ret \equiv \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = bool_value \wedge \mathbf{I}$

$$\frac{}{\langle h; mem_int_1 \text{ binop}_{rel} mem_int_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{done } \langle bool_value \rangle : ret \rangle}$$

MEMOP_IS_INTFROMPTR

1. $mem_int \equiv \text{cast_ptr_to_int } mem_ptr$
2. $ret \equiv \Sigma y:\text{integer}. y = mem_int \wedge \mathbf{I}$

$$\frac{}{\langle h; \text{intFromPtr}(\tau_1, \tau_2, mem_ptr) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{done } \langle mem_int \rangle : ret \rangle}$$

MEMOP_IS_PTRFROMINT

1. $mem_ptr \equiv \text{cast_ptr_to_int } mem_int$
2. $ret \equiv \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = mem_ptr \wedge \mathbf{I}$

$$\frac{}{\langle h; \text{ptrFromInt}(\tau_1, \tau_2, mem_int) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{done } \langle mem_ptr \rangle : ret \rangle}$$

MEMOP_IS_PTRVALIDFORDEREF

1. $\langle h; res_term \rangle \Downarrow \langle h' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (term) \rangle$
2. $pt \equiv term \mapsto_{\tau}^{init} value$
3. $bool_value \equiv \text{aligned}(\tau, term)$
4. $\text{smt}(\cdot \Rightarrow (term = mem_ptr) \wedge (init = \text{const}_{\tau} \text{true}))$
5. $ret \equiv \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{aligned}(\tau, pval) \wedge (mem_ptr \mapsto_{\tau}^{\text{const}_{\tau} \text{true}} value) * \mathbf{I}$

$$\frac{}{\langle h; \text{ptrValidForDeref}(\tau, mem_ptr, res_term) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h' + \{pt \ \& \ \text{None}\}; \text{done } \langle bool_value, \text{Owned } \langle \tau \rangle (mem_ptr) \rangle : ret \rangle}$$

MEMOP_IS_PTRWELLALIGNED

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{bool_value} \equiv \text{aligned}(\tau, \text{mem_ptr}) \\
2. \text{ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{bool}. y = \text{bool_value} \wedge \mathbf{I} \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{ptrWellAligned}(\tau, \text{mem_ptr}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{done} \langle \text{bool_value} \rangle : \text{ret} \rangle
\end{array}$$

MEMOP_IS_PTRARRAYSHIFT

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{mem_ptr}' \equiv \text{mem_ptr} +_{\text{ptr}} (\text{mem_int} \times \text{size.of}(\tau)) \\
2. \text{ret} \equiv \Sigma y:\text{pointer}. y = \text{mem_ptr}' \wedge \mathbf{I} \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{ptrArrayShift}(\text{mem_ptr}, \tau, \text{mem_int}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{done} \langle \text{mem_ptr}' \rangle : \text{ret} \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; \text{is_expr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{is_expr}' \rangle}$$

IS_IS_MEMOP

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; \text{memop} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{tval} : \text{ret} \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{memop}(\text{memop}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{tval} : \text{ret} \rangle
\end{array}$$

IS_IS_ACTION

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; \text{action} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{tval} : \text{ret} \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{action} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{tval} : \text{ret} \rangle
\end{array}$$

IS_IS_NEG_ACTION

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \langle h; \text{action} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{tval} : \text{ret} \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{neg action} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{tval} : \text{ret} \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; \text{seq_expr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{texpr} : \text{ret} \rangle}$$

SEQ_T_CCALL

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{ident} : \text{fun} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals} \\
2. \langle h; \overline{x_i = \text{spine_elem}_i^i} :: \text{fun} \gg \langle h'; \sigma; \text{ret} \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{ccall}(\tau, \text{ident}, \overline{\text{spine_elem}_i^i}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \sigma(\text{texpr}) : \text{ret} \rangle
\end{array}$$

SEQ_T_PROC

$$\begin{array}{l}
1. \text{name} : \text{fun} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals} \\
2. \langle h; \overline{x_i = \text{spine_elem}_i^i} :: \text{fun} \gg \langle h'; \sigma; \text{ret} \rangle \\
\hline
\langle h; \text{pcall}(\text{name}, \overline{\text{spine_elem}_i^i}) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \sigma(\text{texpr}) : \text{ret} \rangle
\end{array}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; \text{seq_texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{texpr} \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_RUN

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{ident:fun} \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto \text{texpr} \in \text{Globals} \\ 2. \langle h; \overline{x_i = pval_i}^i \rangle :: \text{fun} \gg \langle h'; \sigma; \text{false} \wedge \mathbf{I} \rangle \end{array}}{\langle h; \text{run ident } \overline{pval_i}^i \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \sigma(\text{texpr}) \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_CASE

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{pat}_j = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma_j \\ 2. \forall i < j. \text{not}(\text{pat}_i = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma_i) \end{array}}{\langle h; \text{case pval of } \overline{\text{pat}_i \Rightarrow \text{texpr}_i}^i \text{ end} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \sigma_j(\text{texpr}_j) \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LETP_SUB

$$\frac{1. \text{ident_or_pat} = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma}{\langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat} = \text{pval in texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \sigma(\text{texpr}) \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LETP_LETP

$$\frac{1. \langle \text{pexpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{tpval:pure_ret} \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat} = \text{pexpr in texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat:pure_ret} = \text{tpval in texpr} \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LETP_LETP

$$\frac{1. \langle \text{pexpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{texpr:pure_ret} \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat} = \text{pexpr in texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat:pure_ret} = \text{texpr in texpr} \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LETP_SUB

$$\frac{1. \text{ident_or_pat} = \text{pval} \rightsquigarrow \sigma}{\langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat:pure_ret} = \text{done pval in texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \sigma(\text{texpr}) \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LETP_LETP

$$\frac{1. \langle \text{texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle \text{texpr}' \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat:pure_ret} = \text{texpr in texpr} \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; \text{let ident_or_pat:pure_ret} = \text{texpr}' \text{ in texpr} \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LETT_SUB

$$\frac{1. \langle h; \overline{ret_pat_i = ret_term_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let } \overline{ret_pat_i^i}:ret = \text{done } \langle \overline{ret_term_i^i} \rangle \text{ in } texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \sigma(texpr) \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LET_LETT

$$\frac{1. \langle h; seq_expr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr_1:ret \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let } ret_pat = seq_expr \text{ in } texpr_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{let } ret_pat:ret = texpr_1 \text{ in } texpr_2 \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_LETT_LETT

$$\frac{1. \langle h; texpr_1 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr_1' \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let } ret_pat:ret = texpr_1 \text{ in } texpr_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{let } ret_pat:ret = texpr_1' \text{ in } texpr_2 \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_IF_TRUE

$$\overline{\langle h; \text{if True then } texpr_1 \text{ else } texpr_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; texpr_1 \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_IF_FALSE

$$\overline{\langle h; \text{if False then } texpr_1 \text{ else } texpr_2 \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; texpr_2 \rangle}$$

TSEQ_T_BOUND

$$\overline{\langle h; \text{bound } [int](is_texpr) \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; is_texpr \rangle}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; is_texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr \rangle}$$

TIS_T_LETS_SUB

$$\frac{1. \langle h; \overline{ret_pat_i = ret_term_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let strong } \overline{ret_pat_i^i} = \text{done } \langle \overline{ret_term_i^i} \rangle:ret \text{ in } texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \sigma(texpr) \rangle}$$

TIs_T_LETS_LETS

$$\frac{1. \langle h; is_expr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; is_expr' \rangle}{\langle h; \text{let strong } ret_pat = is_expr \text{ in } texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; \text{let strong } ret_pat = is_expr' \text{ in } texpr \rangle}$$

$$\boxed{\langle h; texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr' \rangle}$$

T_T_TSEQ_T

$$\frac{1. \langle h; seq_texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; texpr \rangle}{\langle h; seq_texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h; texpr \rangle}$$

T_T_TIs_T

$$\frac{1. \langle h; is_texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr \rangle}{\langle h; is_texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr \rangle}$$

A6 Miscellaneous

$\boxed{\overline{x}_i^i :: fun \rightsquigarrow C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}$ matching \overline{x}_i^i and fun produces contexts $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$ and return type ret

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{FUN_ENV_RET} \\
 \hline
 ::ret \rightsquigarrow ; ; ; \mid ret
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{FUN_ENV_COMP} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. \overline{x}_i^i :: fun \rightsquigarrow C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}{x, \overline{x}_i^i :: \Pi x:\beta. fun \rightsquigarrow x:\beta, C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{FUN_ENV_LOG} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. \overline{x}_i^i :: fun \rightsquigarrow C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}{x, \overline{x}_i^i :: \forall x:\beta. fun \rightsquigarrow C; x:\beta, \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{FUN_ENV_PHI} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. \overline{x}_i^i :: fun \rightsquigarrow C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}{\overline{x}_i^i :: term \supset fun \rightsquigarrow C; \mathcal{L}; term, \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{FUN_ENV_RES} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. \overline{x}_i^i :: fun \rightsquigarrow C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret}{x, \overline{x}_i^i :: res * fun \rightsquigarrow C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; x:res, \mathcal{R} \mid ret}
 \end{array}$$

$\boxed{C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}$ context weakening: $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$ is stronger than $C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_EMPTY} \\
 \hline
 ; ; ; \sqsubseteq ; ; ;
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_CONS_COMP} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{C, x:\beta; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C', x:\beta; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_CONS_LOG} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{C; \mathcal{L}; x:\beta; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; x:\beta; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_CONS_PHI} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi, term; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi', term; \mathcal{R}'}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_CONS_RES} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}, x:res \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}', x:res}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_SKIP_COMP} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C', x:\beta; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}
 \end{array}
 \quad
 \begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_SKIP_LOG} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; x:\beta; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{WEAK_SKIP_PHI} \\
 \hline
 \frac{1. C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'}{C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq C'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi', term; \mathcal{R}'}
 \end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \mathcal{R})}$ well-typed substitution: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, σ checks against type $(\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \mathcal{R})$. It is complicated by the fact that substitutions are assumed to be sequential/telescoping.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{SUBS_CHK_EMPTY} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{SUBS_CHK_COMP} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{SUBS_CHK_LOG} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{SUBS_CHK_RES} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash [] \Leftarrow (\cdot; \cdot; \cdot) \qquad \frac{1. \mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash pval/x \Leftarrow (x;\beta; \cdot; \cdot)} \qquad \frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash term \Rightarrow \beta}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \cdot \vdash term/x \Leftarrow (\cdot; x;\beta; \cdot)} \qquad \frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term/x \Leftarrow (\cdot; \cdot; x; res)} \\
\\
\text{SUBS_CHK_CONCAT} \\
\frac{1. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash \psi(\sigma) \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_2; \psi(\mathcal{R}'_2)) \quad 2. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1 \vdash \psi \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_1; \mathcal{L}_1; \mathcal{R}'_1)}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}_1, \mathcal{R}_2 \vdash [\psi, \sigma] \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2; \mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2; \mathcal{R}'_1, \mathcal{R}'_2)}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}}$ heap typing: under context $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, heap h checks against context/type $\underline{\mathcal{R}}$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{HEAP_EMPTY} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{HEAP_IF} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{HEAP_PRED_OWNED} \\
\hline
\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \cdot \Leftarrow \cdot \qquad \frac{1. \Phi \vdash \text{if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2 \equiv \text{if } term' \text{ then } res'_1 \text{ else } res'_2}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \{ \text{if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2 \} \Leftarrow \cdot; \text{if } term' \text{ then } res'_1 \text{ else } res'_2} \qquad \frac{1. \Phi \vdash pred \equiv pred' \quad 2. pred \equiv ptr \xrightarrow{init}_\tau value \quad 3. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash init \Rightarrow bool_\tau \quad 4. \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash value \Rightarrow \beta_\tau}{\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \{ pred \ \& \ None \} \Leftarrow \cdot; pred'}
\end{array}$$

HEAP_PRED_OTHER

1. $\Phi \vdash \text{pred_term}(oarg) \equiv \text{pred_term}'(oarg')$
 2. $\text{pred_term} \equiv \alpha(\text{ptr}, \overline{iarg_i^i})$
 3. $\alpha \neq \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$
 4. $\alpha \equiv x_p:\text{pointer}, \overline{x_i:\beta_i^i}, y:\text{record } \overline{tag_j:\beta_j^j} \mapsto \text{res} \in \text{Globals}$
 5. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{def} \Leftarrow [oarg/y, [\overline{iarg_i/x_i^i}], \text{ptr}/x_p](\text{res})$
 6. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \text{heap} \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \{\text{pred_term}(oarg) \& \text{def} \& \text{heap}\} \Leftarrow _:\text{pred_term}'(oarg')$$

HEAP_QPRED_OWNED

1. $\Phi \vdash \text{qpred} \equiv \text{qpred}'$
 2. $\text{qpred} \equiv * x. \text{iguard} \Rightarrow \text{ptr} + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau) \xrightarrow{\text{oarg}[x].\text{init}}_{\tau} \text{oarg}[x].\text{value}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \{\text{qpred} \& \cdot\} \Leftarrow _:\text{qpred}'$$

HEAP_QPRED_OTHER

1. $\Phi \vdash \text{qpred_term}(oarg) \equiv \text{qpred_term}'(oarg')$
 2. $\text{qpred_term}' \equiv (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\}$
 3. $\alpha \neq \text{Owned} \langle \tau \rangle$
 4. $\forall x. \text{iguard} \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \{\alpha(\text{ptr}, \text{iargs})(\text{oarg}[x]) \& \text{arr_def_heap}[x]\} \Leftarrow _:\alpha(\text{ptr}, \text{iargs})(\text{oarg}[x])$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash \{\text{qpred_term}(oarg) \& \text{arr_def_heap}\} \Leftarrow _:\text{qpred_term}'(oarg')$$

HEAP_CONCAT

1. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 2. $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
-
- $$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h + h' \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}, \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}}$ heap typing: under context Φ , heap h checks against context/type $\underline{\mathcal{R}}$

HEAP'_AUX

1. $\cdot; \cdot; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
-
- $$\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash res \sim res'}$ *res is related to res'*

REL_RES_IF

REL_RES_EMP	REL_RES_PHI	
$\Phi \vdash \text{emp} \sim \text{emp}$	$\frac{1. \text{term} \sim \text{term}'}{\Phi \vdash \text{term} \sim \text{term}'}$	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. $\text{term} \sim \text{term}'$ 2. $\text{smt}(\Phi \Rightarrow \text{term} \leftrightarrow \text{term}')$ 3. $\Phi \vdash \text{res}_1 \sim \text{res}'_1$ 4. $\Phi \vdash \text{res}_2 \sim \text{res}'_2$
$\Phi \vdash \text{if term then res}_1 \text{ else res}_2 \sim \text{if term}' \text{ then res}'_1 \text{ else res}'_2$		

REL_RES_EXISTS

$$\frac{1. \forall \text{term} \sim \text{term}'. \Phi \vdash \text{term}/y(\text{res}_1) \sim \text{term}'/y'(\text{res}'_1)}{\Phi \vdash \exists y:\beta. \text{res}_1 \sim \exists y':\beta. \text{res}'_1}$$

REL_RES_SEPCONJ

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \Phi \vdash \text{res}_1 \sim \text{res}'_1 \\ 2. \Phi \vdash \text{res}_2 \sim \text{res}'_2 \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \text{res}_1 * \text{res}_2 \sim \text{res}'_1 * \text{res}'_2}$$

REL_RES_PRED

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{ptr} \sim \text{ptr}' \\ 2. \overline{\text{iarg}_i} \sim \overline{\text{iarg}'_i} \\ 3. \text{oarg} \sim \text{oarg}' \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash \alpha(\text{ptr}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i}^i)(\text{oarg}) \sim \alpha(\text{ptr}', \overline{\text{iarg}'_i}^i)(\text{oarg}')}$$

REL_RES_QPRED

$$\frac{\begin{array}{l} 1. \text{iguard} \sim \text{iguard}' \\ 2. \text{ptr} \sim \text{ptr}' \\ 3. \overline{\text{iarg}_i} \sim \overline{\text{iarg}'_i} \\ 4. \text{oarg} \sim \text{oarg}' \end{array}}{\Phi \vdash (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}_i}^i)\}(\text{oarg}) \sim (x'; \text{iguard}')\{\alpha(\text{ptr}' + x' \times \text{step}, \overline{\text{iarg}'_i}^i)\}(\text{oarg}')}$$

$\boxed{\Phi \vdash fun \sim ret}$ *fun* is related to *ret*

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{REL_RET_I} \\
\hline
\Phi \vdash I \sim I
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{REL_RET_COMP} \\
\frac{1. \forall term \sim pval. \Phi \vdash term/y(fun) \sim pval/y'(ret)}{\Phi \vdash \Pi y:\beta. fun \sim \Sigma y':\beta. ret}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{REL_RET_LOG} \\
\frac{1. \forall oarg \sim oarg'. \Phi \vdash oarg/y(fun) \sim oarg'/y'(ret)}{\Phi \vdash \forall y:\beta. fun \sim \exists y':\beta. ret}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{REL_RET_PHI} \\
\frac{1. term \sim term' \\ 2. \Phi \vdash fun \sim ret}{\Phi \vdash term \supset fun \sim term' \wedge ret}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{REL_RET_RES} \\
\frac{1. \Phi \vdash res \sim res' \\ 2. \Phi \vdash fun \sim ret}{\Phi \vdash res \multimap fun \sim res' * ret}
\end{array}$$

$\boxed{\llbracket spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res}$ specification *spec* (with optional record *opt_ident*) represents resource *res* (*opt_ident* is present return when a return is expected, absent when it is not)

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{SPEC_RES_NONE} \\
\hline
\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket(\text{None}) = \text{emp}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{SPEC_RES_RETURN} \\
\hline
\llbracket \text{return } \{ x_i = term_i^i \}; \rrbracket(y) = (\bigwedge (y.x_i = term_i^i))
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{SPEC_RES_LETTERM} \\
\frac{1. \llbracket spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res}{\llbracket \text{let } y = term; spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = term/y(res)}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\text{SPEC_RES_ASSERT} \\
\frac{1. \llbracket spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res}{\llbracket \text{assert } (term); spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = term * res}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\text{SPEC_RES_ENDIF} \\
\frac{1. \llbracket spec_1 \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res_1 \\ 2. \llbracket spec_2 \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res_2}{\llbracket \text{if } (term) \{ spec_1 \} \text{ else } \{ spec_2 \} \rrbracket(opt_ident) = \text{if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2}
\end{array}$$

SPEC_RES_MIDDLEIF

1. $\llbracket spec_1 \rrbracket(\text{None}) = res_1$
2. $\llbracket spec_2 \rrbracket(\text{None}) = res_2$
3. $\llbracket spec_3 \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res_3$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \text{if } (term) \{ spec_1 \} \text{ else } \{ spec_2 \} spec_3 \rrbracket(opt_ident) = (\text{if } term \text{ then } res_1 \text{ else } res_2) * res_3}$$

SPEC_RES_LETPRED

1. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, _:_i^i, _:\text{record } \overline{tag_j:\beta_j^j} \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals}$
2. $\llbracket spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \text{let } y = \alpha(ptr, iargs); spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = \exists y:\text{record } \overline{tag_j:\beta_j^j}. \alpha(ptr, iargs)(y) * res}$$

SPEC_RES_LETQPRED

1. $qpred_term \equiv (x; iguard)\{\alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs)\}$
2. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, _:_i^i, _:\text{record } \overline{tag_j:\beta_j^j} \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals}$
3. $\llbracket spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = res$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \text{let } y = qpred_term; spec \rrbracket(opt_ident) = \exists y:\text{array record } \overline{tag_j:\beta_j^j}. (x; iguard)\{\alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs)\}(y) * res}$$

$\llbracket spec \rrbracket = norm_ret$ specification $spec$ represents normalised return type $norm_ret$

SPEC_NORMRET_NONE

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket = \mathbf{I}}$$

SPEC_NORMRET_LETTERM

$$\frac{1. \llbracket spec \rrbracket = \underline{ret}}{\llbracket \text{let } y = term; spec \rrbracket = \underline{term/y(\underline{ret})}}$$

SPEC_NORMRET_ASSERT

$$\frac{1. \llbracket spec \rrbracket = \underline{ret}}{\llbracket \text{assert } (term); spec \rrbracket = \underline{term \wedge \underline{ret}}}$$

SPEC_NORMRET_IF

$$\begin{array}{l} 1. \llbracket \text{if } (term) \{ spec_1 \} \text{ else } \{ spec_2 \} \cdot \rrbracket (\text{None}) = \underline{res} \\ 2. \llbracket spec_3 \rrbracket = \underline{ret} \end{array} \frac{}{\llbracket \text{if } (term) \{ spec_1 \} \text{ else } \{ spec_2 \} spec_3 \rrbracket = \underline{res} * \underline{ret}}$$

SPEC_NORMRET_LETPRED

$$\begin{array}{l} 1. \alpha \equiv _ : \text{pointer}, _ : _ : i^i, _ : \text{record } \overline{tag_j : \beta_j^j} \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals} \\ 2. \llbracket spec \rrbracket = \underline{ret} \end{array} \frac{}{\llbracket \text{let } y = \alpha(ptr, iargs); spec \rrbracket = \exists y : \text{record } \overline{tag_j : \beta_j^j}. \alpha(ptr, iargs)(y) * \underline{ret}}$$

SPEC_NORMRET_LETQPRED

$$\begin{array}{l} 1. qpred_term \equiv (x; iguard) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \} \\ 2. \alpha \equiv _ : \text{pointer}, _ : _ : i^i, _ : \text{record } \overline{tag_j : \beta_j^j} \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals} \\ 3. \llbracket spec \rrbracket = \underline{ret} \end{array} \frac{}{\llbracket \text{let } y = qpred_term; spec \rrbracket = \exists y : \text{array record } \overline{tag_j : \beta_j^j}. (x; iguard) \{ \alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs) \} (y) * \underline{ret}}$$

$\llbracket spec \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{norm_fun}$ specification $spec$ represents normalised argument type $\underline{norm_fun}$

SPEC_NORMARG_NONE

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \cdot \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{ret}}$$

SPEC_NORMARG_LETTERM

$$\frac{1. \llbracket spec \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{fun}}{\llbracket \text{let } y = term; spec \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{term/y(fun)}}$$

SPEC_NORMARG_ASSERT

$$\frac{1. \llbracket spec \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{fun}}{\llbracket \text{assert } (term); spec \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{term \supset fun}}$$

SPEC_NORMARG_IF

$$\begin{array}{l} 1. \llbracket \text{if } (term) \{ spec_1 \} \text{ else } \{ spec_2 \} \cdot \rrbracket (\text{None}) = \underline{res} \\ 2. \llbracket spec_3 \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{fun} \end{array} \frac{}{\llbracket \text{if } (term) \{ spec_1 \} \text{ else } \{ spec_2 \} spec_3 \mid \underline{ret} \rrbracket = \underline{res} * \underline{fun}}$$

SPEC_NORMARG_LETPRED

1. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, _:\overline{x_i}^i, _:\text{record } \overline{\text{tag}_j:\beta_j^j} \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals}$
2. $\llbracket \text{spec} \mid \underline{\text{ret}} \rrbracket = \underline{\text{fun}}$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \text{let } y = \alpha(\text{ptr}, \text{iargs}); \text{spec} \mid \underline{\text{ret}} \rrbracket = \forall y:\text{record } \overline{\text{tag}_j:\beta_j^j}. \alpha(\text{ptr}, \text{iargs})(y) \text{ -* } \underline{\text{fun}}}$$

SPEC_NORMARG_LETQPRED

1. $qpred_term \equiv (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\}$
2. $\alpha \equiv _:\text{pointer}, _:\overline{x_i}^i, _:\text{record } \overline{\text{tag}_j:\beta_j^j} \mapsto _ \in \text{Globals}$
3. $\llbracket \text{spec} \mid \underline{\text{ret}} \rrbracket = \underline{\text{fun}}$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \text{let } y = qpred_term; \text{spec} \mid \underline{\text{ret}} \rrbracket = \forall y:\text{array record } \overline{\text{tag}_j:\beta_j^j}. (x; \text{iguard})\{\alpha(\text{ptr} + x \times \text{step}, \text{iargs})\}(y) \text{ -* } \underline{\text{fun}}}$$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \tau\text{name}(\overline{\tau_i x_i^i}) \text{ requires } \text{spec}_1 \text{ ensures } \text{spec}_2 \rrbracket = \underline{\text{norm_fun}}}$$

user-defined C function specification represents normalised argument

type $\underline{\text{norm_fun}}$

SPEC_USERDEF_CFUNC_BASE

1. $\llbracket \text{spec}_2 \rrbracket = \underline{\text{ret}}$
2. $\llbracket \text{spec}_1 \mid \Sigma y:\beta_\tau. \underline{\text{ret}} \rrbracket = \underline{\text{fun}}$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \tau\text{name}() \text{ requires } \text{spec}_1 \text{ ensures } \text{spec}_2 \rrbracket = \underline{\text{fun}}}$$

SPEC_USERDEF_CFUNC_ARG

1. $\llbracket \tau\text{name}(\overline{\tau_i x_i^i}) \text{ requires } \text{spec}_1 \text{ ensures } \text{spec}_2 \rrbracket = \underline{\text{fun}}$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \tau\text{name}(\tau_1 x_1, \overline{\tau_i x_i^i}) \text{ requires } \text{spec}_1 \text{ ensures } \text{spec}_2 \rrbracket = \underline{\Pi x_1:\beta_{\tau_1}. \text{fun}}}$$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \text{predicate } \{ \overline{\beta'_j y_j^j} \} \alpha(\overline{\beta_i x_i^i}) \{ \text{spec} \} \rrbracket = \alpha' \equiv \overline{r_k:\beta''_k^k} \mapsto \text{res}}$$

user-defined resource predicate definition represents predicate

SPEC_PREDDEF_PRED

1. $\llbracket \text{spec} \rrbracket(y) = \text{res}$

$$\frac{}{\llbracket \text{predicate } \{ \overline{\beta'_j y_j^j} \} \alpha(\text{pointer } x_p, \overline{\beta_i x_i^i}) \{ \text{spec} \} \rrbracket = \alpha \equiv x_p:\text{pointer}, \overline{x_i:\beta_i^i}, y:\text{record } \overline{y_j:\beta'_j^j} \mapsto \text{res}}$$

A7 Metvars and Grammar

<i>ident, x, x_p, y, y_p, y_f, -, abbrev, r</i>	subscripts: p for pointers, f for functions
<i>n, i, j, k</i>	index variables
<i>impl_const</i>	implementation-defined constant
<i>member</i>	C struct/union member name
	Ott-hack, ignore (annotations)
<i>nat</i>	OCaml arbitrary-width natural number
<i>mem_ptr</i>	abstract pointer value
<i>mem_val</i>	abstract memory value
	Ott-hack, ignore (locations)
<i>mem_iv_c</i>	OCaml type for memory constraints on integer values
<i>UB_name</i>	undefined behaviour
<i>string, List</i>	OCaml string
	Ott-hack, ignore (OCaml type variable TY)
\mathbb{Q}	OCaml type for rational numbers
	Ott-hack, ignore (OCaml Symbol.prefix)
<i>mem_order, -</i>	OCaml type for memory order
<i>linux_mem_order</i>	OCaml type for Linux memory order
	Ott-hack, ignore (OCaml type variable bt)

<i>int, -, step</i>	::=	OCaml fixed-width integer
		<i>i</i>
		literal integer
		<code>size_of(τ)</code> M
		size of a C type
<i>Sctypes_t, τ</i>	::=	partial/relevant grammar of C types
		<code>array int τ</code>
		fixed-length array of element type τ
		<code>int</code>
		C (signed) integer
		τ^*
		pointer to type τ

		struct <i>tag</i>	
		C struct type	
<i>tag, init, value</i>	::=	OCaml type for struct/union tag	
		<i>ident</i>	
$\beta, -$::=	base types	
		unit	
		unit	
		bool	
		boolean	
		integer	
		integer	
		real	
		rational numbers?	
		pointer	
		location	
		struct <i>tag</i>	
		C structs	
		record $\overline{tag_i:\beta_i}^i$	
		res. pred. output arguments	
		map $\beta \beta'$	
		map	
		array $\beta \quad M$	
		array (integer-indexed map)	
		list β	
		list	
		$\overline{\beta_i}^i$	
		tuple	
		set β	
		set	
		bool $_{\tau}$ M	
		boolean from C type	

		β_T	M
		of a C type	
<i>binop</i>	::=	binary operators	
		+	addition
		-	subtraction
		*	multiplication
		/	division
		mod	modulus
		rem	remainder
		^	exponentiation
		=	equality, defined both for integer and C types
		!=	inequality, similiarly defined
		>	greater than, similarly defined
		<	less than, similarly defined
		>=	greater than or equal to, similarly defined
		<=	less than or equal to, similarly defined
		&	conjunction
		\	

disjunction

<i>binop_{arith}</i>	::=	arithmetic binary operators
		+
		-
		*
		/
		mod
		rem
		^
<i>binop_{rel}</i>	::=	relational binary operators
		=
		!=
		>
		<
		>=
		<=
<i>binop_{bool}</i>	::=	boolean binary operators
		∧
		∨
<i>mem_{int}</i>	::=	memory integer value
		1 M
		0 M
<i>object_{value}</i>	::=	C object values (inhabitants of object types), which can be read/stored
		<i>mem_{int}</i>
		integer value
		<i>mem_{ptr}</i>
		pointer value

		$\text{array}(\overline{\text{loaded_value}_i}^i)$
		C array value
		$(\text{struct } \text{ident})\{\overline{\text{member}_i:\tau_i = \text{mem_val}_i}^i\}$
		C struct value
		$(\text{union } \text{ident})\{\text{member} = \text{mem_val}\}$
		C union value
<i>loaded_value</i>	::=	potentially unspecified C object values
		specified <i>object_value</i>
		specified loaded value
<i>value</i>	::=	Core values
		<i>object_value</i>
		C object value
		<i>loaded_value</i>
		loaded C object value
		Unit
		unit
		True
		boolean true
		False
		boolean false
		$\beta[\overline{\text{value}_i}^i]$
		list
		$(\overline{\text{value}_i}^i)$
		tuple
<i>bool_value</i>	::=	Core booleans
		True
		boolean true
		False
		boolean false

ctor_val ::= data constructors (values, do not reduce)
| Nil β
empty list
| Cons
list cons
| Tuple
tuple
| Array
C fixed-size array (guaranteed to be non-empty)
| Specified
non-unspecified loaded value

ctor_expr ::= data constructors (expressions, do reduce)
| IvCOMPL
bitwise complement
| IvAND
bitwise AND
| IvOR
bitwise OR
| IvXOR
bitwise XOR
| Fvfromint
cast integer to floating value
| Ivfromfloat
cast floating to integer value

name ::=
| *ident*
Core identifier
| *impl_const*
implementation-defined constant

pval ::= pure values

		<i>ident</i>	
		Core identifier	
		<i>impl_const</i>	
		implementation-defined constant	
		<i>value</i>	
		Core values	
		constrained ($\overline{mem_iv_c_i}, \overline{pval_i^i}$)	
		constrained value	
		<i>ctor_val</i> ($\overline{pval_i^i}$)	
		data constructor application	
		(struct <i>ident</i>){ $\overline{member_i = pval_i^i}$ }	
		C struct expression	
		(union <i>ident</i>){ <i>member = pval</i> }	
		C union expression	
		$\sigma(pval)$	M
		substitution for pure values	
<i>pvals</i>	::=	list of pure values	
		$\overline{pval_i^i}$	
		$\sigma(pvals)$	M
<i>tpval</i>	::=	top-level pure values	
		done <i>pval</i>	
		pure done	
		undef <i>UB_name</i>	
		undefined behaviour	
		error (<i>string</i> , <i>pval</i>)	
		impl-defined static error	
<i>ident_opt_β</i>	::=	type annotated optional identifier	
		$_{:}\beta$	binders = {}
		<i>ident</i> : β	binders = <i>ident</i>

pat ::= computational patterns
| *ident_opt_β* binders = binders(*ident_opt_β*)
| *ctor_val*(\overline{pat}_i^i) binders = binders(\overline{pat}_i^i)

ident_or_pat ::= identifier or pattern
| *ident* binders = *ident*
| *pat* binders = binders(*pat*)

z ::= OCaml arbitrary-width integer
| *i* M
literal integer
| *int* M
| *mem_int* M
convert *mem_int* to an integer
| *mem_ptr* M
convert *mem_ptr* to an ptreger
| *offset_of_tag*(*member*) M
offset of a struct member
| *ptr_size* M
size of a pointer
| *max_int*_τ M
maximum value of int of type τ
| *min_int*_τ M
minimum value of int of type τ

bool, _ ::= OCaml booleans
| **true**
| **false**
| *bool*||*bool'* M

lit ::=
| *ident*

		z	
		z	
		\mathbb{Q}	
		<i>bool</i>	
		unit	
		default β	
		null	
<i>arith_op</i>	::=	SMT term arithmetic operations	
		$term_1 + term_2$	
		$term_1 - term_2$	
		$term_1 \times term_2$	
		$term_1 / term_2$	
		$term_1 \bmod term_2$	
		$term_1 \bmod term_2$	
		$term_1 \uparrow term_2$	
		$term_1 \text{ binop}_{arith} term_2$	M
<i>bool_op</i>	::=	SMT term boolean operations	
		$\bigwedge(\overline{term_i}^i)$	
		$\bigvee(\overline{term_i}^i)$	
		$term_1 \rightarrow term_2$	
		$term_1 \leftrightarrow term_2$	M
		$\neg term$	
		if $term_1$ then $term_2$ else $term_3$	
		$term_1 = term_2$	
		$term_1 \neq term_2$	M
		$term_1 \text{ binop}_{bool} term_2$	M
<i>tuple_op</i>	::=	SMT term tuple constructor and projections	
		$(\overline{term_i}^i)$	
		$term^{(int)}$	

<i>struct_op</i>	::=	SMT term for struct field-projection	
		<i>term.member</i>	
<i>record_op</i>	::=	SMT term for record operations	
		$\{\overline{ident_i = term_i}^i\}$	
		<i>term.ident</i>	
<i>pointer_op</i>	::=	SMT term pointer operations	
		$term_1 +_{ptr} term_2$	
		<code>cast_int_to_ptr</code> <i>term</i>	
		<code>cast_ptr_to_int</code> <i>term</i>	
<i>list_op</i>	::=	SMT term list constructors and operations	
		<code>nil</code>	
		$term_1 :: term_2$	
		<code>t1</code> <i>term</i>	
		$term^{(int)}$	
<i>ct_pred</i>	::=	SMT predicates for C-types	
		<code>representable</code> (τ , <i>term</i>)	
		<code>aligned</code> (τ , <i>term</i>)	
		<code>alignedI</code> (<i>term</i> ₁ , <i>term</i> ₂)	
<i>cmp_op</i>	::=	SMT term relational operations	
		$term_1 < term_2$	
		$term_1 \leq term_2$	
		$term_1 \text{ binop}_{rel} term_2$	M
<i>map_op</i>	::=	SMT term map operations	
		$[\overline{term_i}^i]$	M
		array literal	
		$term_1[term_2]$	

		const <i>term</i>	
		$term_1[term_2] := term_3$	
		<i>ident</i> : β . <i>term</i>	
<i>term</i> , <i>iguard</i> , <i>ptr</i> , <i>init</i> , <i>-</i> , <i>value</i> , <i>iarg</i> , <i>oarg</i>	::=	SMT term grammar	
		<i>lit</i>	
		<i>arith_op</i>	
		<i>bool_op</i>	
		<i>cmp_op</i>	
		<i>tuple_op</i>	
		<i>struct_op</i>	
		<i>record_op</i>	
		<i>pointer_op</i>	
		<i>list_op</i>	
		<i>ct_pred</i>	
		<i>map_op</i>	
		<i>string</i> (<i>term</i> ₁ , .., <i>term</i> _{<i>n</i>})	
		(<i>term</i>)	S
		parentheses	
		σ (<i>term</i>)	M
		substitute σ in <i>term</i>	
		<i>pvals</i>	M
		translate pure values <i>pvals</i> into corresponding SMT term	
		const _{τ} <i>bool</i>	M
		term with structure corresponding to τ	
<i>iargs</i> , <i>-</i>	::=	list of terms (predicate input-arguments)	
		\overline{iarg}_i	
		σ (<i>iargs</i>)	M
<i>qterm</i>	::=	quantified SMT terms	
		<i>term</i>	
		unquantified SMT term	

		$\forall ident. term$ universally quantified SMT term	
		$\exists ident. term$ existentially quantified SMT term	
		$\sigma(qterm)$ substitute σ into $qterm$	M
$pred_term$::=	predicate term/request $\alpha(ptr, iargs)$ first parameter must be a pointer	
$qpred_term$::=	quantified predicate term/request $(x; iguard)\{\alpha(ptr + x \times step, iargs)\}$ bind x in $iargs$ $iguard$, ptr and $step$ must be specified each $qpred_term$	S
res_req	::=	resource request $pred_term$ request a resource predicate $qpred_term$ request a quantified resource predicate	
$pred_name, \alpha$::=	names of predicates Owned $\langle \tau \rangle$ sep. logic points-to indexed by C type τ <i>string</i> user-defined name	
$pred, points_to, pt$::=	<i>precise</i> separation-logic predicates $pred_term(oarg)$ a predicate-type is simply the term with an output argument $ptr \xrightarrow{init}_{\tau} value$	S

pretty-printing for points-to predicate $\text{Owned}\langle\tau\rangle(ptr,)\&\{init, value\}$

$qpred, qpoints_to, qpt$::= quantified (integer-indexed) separation logic predicate
 | $qpred_term(oarg)$
 a qpredicate-type is simply the term with an array output argument
 | $* x. iguard \Rightarrow ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau) \xrightarrow{oarg[x].init} oarg[x].value \ S$
 pretty-printing for quantified points-to predicate $* x. iguard \Rightarrow \text{Owned}\langle\tau\rangle(ptr + x \times \text{size_of}(\tau), oarg[x])$

$res, _$::= resources
 | **emp**
 empty heap
 | $term$
 logical assertion, implicitly with emp
 | $pred$
 heap predicate
 | $qpred$
 quantified (integer-indexed) heap predicate
 | $res_1 * res_2$
 separating conjunction
 | $* (\overline{res}_i^i)$ M
 notation for nested sep. conj.
 | $\exists ident:\beta. res$
 existential
 | **if term then res₁ else res₂**
 conditional resource / ordered disjunction
 | $\sigma(res)$ M
 substitute σ in res

\underline{res}, rem ::= normalised resources

		<code>if term then res₁ else res₂</code>	
		conditional resource / ordered disjunction	
		<code>pred</code>	
		heap predicate	
		<code>qpred</code>	
		quantified (integer-indexed) heap predicate	
<code>opt_res</code>	::=	optional resource	
		<code>None</code>	
		<code>res</code>	
<code>ret, _</code>	::=	return types	
		$\Sigma ident:\beta. ret$	
		return a computational value	
		$\exists ident:\beta. ret$	
		return a logical (output) value	
		<code>res * ret</code>	
		return a resource	
		<code>term \wedge ret</code>	
		guarantee a constraint (post-condition)	
		<code>I</code>	
		end return list	
		$\sigma(ret)$	M
		substitute σ in <code>ret</code>	
<code>pure_ret</code>	::=	pure return types	
		$\Sigma ident:\beta. pure_ret$	
		<code>term \wedge pure_ret</code>	
		<code>I</code>	
		$\sigma(pure_ret)$	M
		substitute σ in <code>pure_ret</code>	

ret ::= normalised return types
 | $\Sigma \text{ident}:\beta. \underline{ret}$
 | $\exists \text{ident}:\beta. \underline{ret}$
 | $\underline{res} * \underline{ret}$
 | $\text{term} \wedge \underline{ret}$
 | **I**
 | $\sigma(\underline{ret})$ M

pexpr ::= pure expressions
 | *pval*
 pure values
 | $\text{ctor_expr}(\overline{pval}_i^i)$
 data constructor application
 | $\text{array_shift}(pval_1, \tau, pval_2)$
 pointer array shift
 | $\text{member_shift}(pval, \text{ident}, \text{member})$
 pointer struct/union member shift
 | $\text{not}(pval)$
 boolean not
 | $pval_1 \text{ binop } pval_2$
 binary operations
 | $\text{memberof}(\text{ident}, \text{member}, pval)$
 C struct/union member access
 | $\text{name}(\overline{pval}_i^i)$
 pure function call
 | $\text{assert_undef}(pval, \text{UB_name})$
 if *pval* then UB for reason *UB_name*
 | $\text{bool_to_integer}(pval)$
 convert boolean *pval* to integer
 | $\text{conv_int}(\tau, pval)$
 convert between different integer types
 | $\text{wrapI}(\tau, pval)$
 wrap integer

		$\sigma(pexpr)$ substitution for pure expressions	M
<i>texpr</i>	::=	top-level pure expressions	
		<i>tpval</i> top-level pure values	
		case <i>pval</i> of $\overline{texpr_case_branch_i}$ end pat matching	
		let <i>ident_or_pat</i> = <i>pexpr</i> in <i>texpr</i> pure let	bind binders(<i>ident_or_pat</i>) in <i>texpr</i>
		let <i>ident_or_pat</i> : <i>pure_ret</i> = <i>texpr</i> ₁ in <i>texpr</i> ₂ annotated pure let	bind binders(<i>ident_or_pat</i>) in <i>texpr</i> ₂
		if <i>pval</i> then <i>texpr</i> ₁ else <i>texpr</i> ₂ pure if	
		$\sigma(texpr)$ substitute σ in <i>texpr</i>	M
<i>texpr_case_branch</i>	::=	pure top-level case expression branch	
		<i>pat</i> \Rightarrow <i>texpr</i> top-level case expression branch	bind binders(<i>pat</i>) in <i>texpr</i>
<i>m_kill_kind</i>	::=	dynamic static τ	
<i>pred_ops</i>	::=	(q)points-to operation terms	
		iterate (<i>res_term</i> , <i>int</i>) transform points-to-array into quantified points-to	
		congeal (<i>res_term</i> , <i>int</i>) transform quantified points-to into points-to-array	
		explode (<i>res_term</i>) transform points-to-struct into member points-tos	

		implode (<i>res_term</i> , <i>tag</i>)	
		transform member points-tos into points-to-struct	
		break (<i>res_term</i> , <i>term</i>)	
		break a qpred into a qpred and a pred	
		glue (<i>res_term</i>)	
		glue a qpred and a pred (back) into a qpred	
		inj (<i>res_term</i> , <i>ptr</i> , <i>step</i> , <i>x</i> . <i>iargs</i>)	
		transform a pred into a singleton qpred	
		split (<i>res_term</i> , <i>iguard</i>)	
		split a qpred into two qpreds along <i>iguard</i>	
<i>res_term</i> , _	::=	resource terms	
		emp	
		empty heap	
		term	
		term for assertion	
		<i>pred_term</i>	
		heap predicate	
		<i>qpred_term</i>	
		quantified (integer-indexed) heap predicate	
		<i>ident</i>	
		variable	
		$\langle \overline{res_term}_i^i \rangle$	
		(nested) seperating-conjunction pair	
		pack (<i>oarg</i> , <i>res_term</i>)	
		packing for existentials	
		fold <i>res_term</i> : <i>pred</i>	
		fold into recursive res. pred.	
		<i>pred_ops</i>	
		(q)predicate operation terms	
		(<i>res_term</i>)	S
		parentheses	
		σ (<i>res_term</i>)	M

substitution for resource terms

res_val, def ::= resource terms values
| emp
| empty heap
| term
| term for assertion
| *pred_term*
| heap predicate
| *qpred_term*
| quantified (integer-indexed) heap predicate
| $\langle \overline{res_val}_i^i \rangle$
| (nested) separating-conjunction pair
| **pack** (*oarg, res_val*)
| packing for existentials
| (*res_val*) S
| parentheses
| $\sigma(res_val)$ M
| substitution for resource terms

action ::= memory actions
| **create** (*pval, τ*)
| **create_readonly** (*pval₁, τ , pval₂*)
| **alloc** (*pval₁, pval₂*)
| **kill** (*m_kill_kind, pval, res_term*)
| **store** (*bool, τ , pval₁, pval₂, mem_order, res_term*)
| true means store is locking
| **load** (*τ , pval, mem_order, res_term*)
| **rmw** (*τ , pval₁, pval₂, pval₃, mem_order₁, mem_order₂*)
| **fence** (*mem_order*)
| **cmp_exch_strong** (*τ , pval₁, pval₂, pval₃, mem_order₁, mem_order₂*)
| **cmp_exch_weak** (*τ , pval₁, pval₂, pval₃, mem_order₁, mem_order₂*)
| **linux_fence** (*linux_mem_order*)

		<code>linux_load</code> ($\tau, pval, linux_mem_order$)
		<code>linux_store</code> ($\tau, pval_1, pval_2, linux_mem_order$)
		<code>linux_rmw</code> ($\tau, pval_1, pval_2, linux_mem_order$)
<i>polarity</i>	::=	polarities for memory actions
		(pos) sequenced by <code>let weak</code> and <code>let strong</code>
		<code>neg</code>
		only sequenced by <code>let strong</code>
<i>pol_mem_action</i>	::=	memory actions with polarity
		<i>polarity action</i>
<i>memop</i>	::=	operations involving the memory state
		<code>pval₁ binop_{rel} pval₂</code>
		pointer relational binary operations
		<code>pval₁ -_{τ} pval₂</code>
		pointer subtraction
		<code>intFromPtr</code> ($\tau_1, \tau_2, pval$)
		cast pointer value to integer value
		<code>ptrFromInt</code> ($\tau_1, \tau_2, pval$)
		cast integer value to pointer value
		<code>ptrValidForDeref</code> ($\tau, pval, res_term$)
		dereferencing validity predicate
		<code>ptrWellAligned</code> ($\tau, pval$)
		<code>ptrArrayShift</code> ($pval_1, \tau, pval_2$)
		<code>memcpy</code> ($pval_1, pval_2, pval_3$)
		<code>memcmp</code> ($pval_1, pval_2, pval_3$)
		<code>realloc</code> ($pval_1, pval_2, pval_3$)
		<code>va_start</code> ($pval_1, pval_2$)
		<code>va_copy</code> ($pval$)
		<code>va_arg</code> ($pval, \tau$)
		<code>va_end</code> ($pval$)

$ret_term, spine_elem ::=$ return values / spine element
| $pval$
pure computational value
| $oarg$
logical value
| res_term
resource term
| $\sigma(ret_term)$ M
substitution for return values / spine elements

$ret_terms, spine ::=$ return values / spine
| ret_term, ret_terms M
| $\overline{ret_term}_i^i$

$tval ::=$ (effectful) top-level values
| **done** $\langle ret_terms \rangle$
end of top-level expression
| **undef** UB_name
undefined behaviour
| **error** $(string, pval)$
impl-defined static error
| $\sigma(tval)$ M
substitution for top-level values

$res_pat ::=$ resource patterns
| **emp** binders = {}
empty heap
| **term** binders = {}
logical assertion token
| $ident$ binders = $ident$
variable
| **fold** (res_pat) binders = {}
unfold (recursive) predicate

	$\langle res_pat_1, res_pat_2 \rangle$ seperating-conjunction pair	$binders = binders(res_pat_1) \cup binders(res_pat_2)$
	pack ($ident, res_pat$) packing for existentials	$binders = ident \cup binders(res_pat)$
ret_pat	::= return pat	
	comp $ident_or_pat$ computational pattern	$binders = binders(ident_or_pat)$
	log $ident$ logical variable	$binders = ident$
	res res_pat resource pattern	$binders = binders(res_pat)$
	$\overline{ret_pat}_i^i$ sequence of return patterns	$binders = binders(\overline{ret_pat}_i^i)$
seq_expr	::= sequential (effectful) expressions	
	ccall ($\tau, ident, spine$) C function call	
	pcall ($name, spine$) procedure call	
	$\sigma(seq_expr)$	M
seq_texpr	::= sequential top-level (effectful) expressions	
	$tval$ (effectful) top-level values	
	run $ident \overline{pval}_i^i$ run from label	
	let $ident_or_pat = pexpr$ in $texpr$ pure let	bind $binders(ident_or_pat)$ in $texpr$
	let $ident_or_pat:pure_ret = tpepr$ in $texpr$ annotated pure let	bind $binders(ident_or_pat)$ in $texpr$
	let $ret_pat = seq_expr$ in $texpr$ bind return pats	bind $binders(ret_pat)$ in $texpr$

		<code>let <i>ret_pat</i>:<i>ret</i> = <i>expr</i>₁ in <i>expr</i>₂</code>	bind <code>binders(<i>ret_pat</i>)</code> in <i>expr</i> ₂
		annotated bind return pats	
		<code>case <i>pval</i> of $\overline{\text{expr_case_branch}_i}^i$ end</code>	pat matching
		<code>if <i>pval</i> then <i>expr</i>₁ else <i>expr</i>₂</code>	conditional
		<code>bound [<i>int</i>](<i>is_expr</i>)</code>	limit scope of indet seq behaviour, absent at runtime
		<code>insert_lets (<i>res_bind</i>, <i>seq_expr</i>)</code>	M insert let expressions for binding resources
<i>expr_case_branch</i>	::=	top-level case expression branch	
		<code><i>pat</i> ⇒ <i>expr</i></code>	bind <code>binders(<i>pat</i>)</code> in <i>expr</i>
		top-level case expression branch	
<i>is_expr</i>	::=	indet seq (effectful) expressions	
		<code><i>tval</i>:<i>ret</i></code>	(effectful) top-level values
		<code>memop (<i>memop</i>)</code>	pointer op involving memory
		<code><i>pol_mem_action</i></code>	memory action
		<code>pack α(<i>pval</i>, <i>pvals</i>)</code>	fold a predicate
		<code>unpack α(<i>pval</i>, <i>pvals</i>)</code>	unfold a predicate
<i>is_expr</i>	::=	indet seq top-level (effectful) expressions	
		<code>let weak <i>ret_pat</i> = <i>is_expr</i> in <i>expr</i></code>	bind <code>binders(<i>ret_pat</i>)</code> in <i>expr</i> weak sequencing
		<code>let strong <i>ret_pat</i> = <i>is_expr</i> in <i>expr</i></code>	bind <code>binders(<i>ret_pat</i>)</code> in <i>expr</i> strong sequencing

$expr$::= top-level (effectful) expressions
| seq_expr
sequential (effectful) expressions
| is_expr
indet seq (effectful) expressions
| $insert_lets(res_bind, expr)$ M
insert let expressions for binding resources
| $\sigma(expr)$ M
substitute σ in $expr$

fun ::= function types
| $\Pi ident:\beta. fun$
assume a computational value
| $\forall ident:\beta. fun$
assume a logical value
| $res \multimap fun$
assume a resource
| $term \supset fun$
assume a constraint (pre-condition)
| ret
return a value of type ret
| $to_fun ret$ M
change a return to an argument type
| $\sigma(fun)$ M
substitute σ in fun

$pure_fun$::= pure function types
| $\Pi ident:\beta. pure_fun$
| $term \supset pure_fun$
| $pure_ret$

\underline{fun} ::= normalised function types
| $\Pi ident:\beta. \underline{fun}$

		assume a computational value
		$\forall \text{ident}:\beta. \underline{\text{fun}}$
		assume a logical value
		$\underline{\text{res}} \rightarrow * \underline{\text{fun}}$
		assume a resource
		$\text{term} \supset \underline{\text{fun}}$
		assume a constraint (pre-condition)
		$\underline{\text{ret}}$
		return a value of type $\underline{\text{ret}}$
		$\text{to_fun } \underline{\text{ret}} \quad \text{M}$
		change a return to an arugment type
		$\sigma(\underline{\text{fun}}) \quad \text{M}$
		substitute σ in $\underline{\text{fun}}$
σ, ψ	::=	substitutions
		$\text{ret_term}/\text{ident}$
		sub ret_term for ident
		$[\overline{\sigma}_i^i]$
		sequential substitutions
		$\cdot \quad \text{M}$
		empty substitution
		$\sigma(\psi) \quad \text{M}$
		apply σ to all elements in ψ
opt_ident	::=	optional identifier
		None
		ident
spec_expr	::=	expressions for specifications
		term
		pred_term
		qpred_term

$spec$	$::=$ alternative, C-programmer friendly syntax for defining predicates and writing specifications . empty specification $\mathbf{return} \{ \overline{ident_i = term_i^i} \};$ specify output arguments $\mathbf{let} \textit{ident} = \textit{spec_expr}; \textit{spec}$ bind either terms, or output arguments of resource (q)predicates $\mathbf{assert} (\textit{term}); \textit{spec}$ assert specification $\mathbf{if} (\textit{term}) \{ \textit{spec}_1 \} \mathbf{else} \{ \textit{spec}_2 \} \textit{spec}_3$ conditional specification
$user_def$	$::=$ syntax for user-defined predicates and function specifications (pre- and post-conditions) $\mathbf{predicate} \{ \overline{\beta_j^i \textit{tag}_j^j} \} \alpha (\overline{\beta_i \textit{x}_i^i}) \{ \textit{spec} \}$ $\tau\mathbf{name} (\overline{\tau_i \textit{x}_i^i}) \mathbf{requires} \textit{spec}_1 \mathbf{ensures} \textit{spec}_2$
\mathcal{C}	$::=$ computational variable context $\textit{ident}:\beta$ add to context $\overline{\mathcal{C}_i^i}$ concatenate contexts . M empty context
\mathcal{L}	$::=$ logical variable context $\textit{ident}:\beta$ add to context $\overline{\mathcal{L}_i^i}$ concatenate contexts . M empty context

Φ	$::=$ constraints environment $ $ <i>term</i> add to context $ $ $\overline{\Phi}_i^i$ concatenate contexts $ $ \cdot M empty context $ $ $\sigma(\Phi)$ M substitute σ over all constraints in Φ
\mathcal{R}	$::=$ resource environment $ $ <i>ident:res</i> add to context $ $ $\overline{\mathcal{R}}_i^i$ concatenate contexts $ $ \cdot M empty context $ $ $\sigma(\mathcal{R})$ M substitute σ over all SMT terms in all resource types in \mathcal{R}
$\underline{\mathcal{R}}, \text{Rem}, \text{Fr}$	$::=$ normalised resource env $ $ <i>ident:res</i> add to context $ $ $\overline{\mathcal{R}}_i^i$ concatenate contexts $ $ \cdot M empty context $ $ $\sigma(\mathcal{R})$ M substitute σ over all SMT terms in all resource types in \mathcal{R}
<i>ty_extra</i>	$::=$ extra judgements for explicit and inference typing systems $ $ smt ($\Phi \Rightarrow qterm$) check if <i>qterm</i> is SMT-provable in constraint context Φ

$ident:\beta \in \mathcal{C}$
lookup type of $ident$ in context \mathcal{C}

$struct\ tag \ \& \ \overline{member_i:\tau_i}^i \in \mathbf{Globals}$
lookup types of struct tag fields in $\mathbf{Globals}$

$\alpha \equiv \overline{x_i:\beta_i}^i \mapsto res \in \mathbf{Globals}$
lookup body of resource predicate α in $\mathbf{Globals}$

$\mathcal{C} \vdash mem_val \Rightarrow \beta$
dependent on memory object model

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L} \vdash term \Rightarrow \beta$
omitted/assumed definition: $term$ is (a) well-formed (b) annotated with β

$pred_name_1 \neq pred_name_2$
check if $pred_name_1$ and $pred_name_2$ are unequal

$formula ::=$

$judgement$

ty_extra

$opsem_extra$

$misc_extra$

$res \equiv res'$
resource type abbreviation

$res_term \equiv res_term'$
resource term abbreviation

$ret \equiv ret'$
return type abbreviation

$term \equiv term'$
SMT term / constraint abbreviation

$texpr \equiv texpr'$
top-level expression abbreviation

$name: pure_fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto texpr \in \mathbf{Globals}$
lookup type and body of pure function $name$ in $\mathbf{Globals}$

$name: fun \equiv \overline{x_i}^i \mapsto texpr \in \mathbf{Globals}$

lookup type and body of function *name* in `Globals`

res_diff ::= resource difference
| `None`
not possible to take a difference
| *res_term* and *oarg*
request is satisfied exactly by *res_term* and the output argument is *oarg*
| *oarg* and *res_req*
request is satisfied partially with output argument *oarg* with remaining *res_req*
| `bind res_pat1:res1 = res_term1 for ident1 & oarg and ident2:rem`
deconstruct *res_term₁:res₁* using *res_pat₁* to satisfy request exactly (using *ident₁* and *oarg*) with remainder *ident₂:rem*

res_bind ::= resource bindings
| `.`
empty resource binding
| *res_pat:res = res_term*
match *res_term:res* against *res_pat*
| $\overline{res_bind_i}^i$
concatenate resource bindings

opt_term ::= optional SMT term
| `None`
| *term*

cmp ::= result of binary comparison
| `Lt`
less-than
| `Eq`
equals

		Gt	
		greater-than	
<i>opt_cmp</i>	::=	optional result of binary comparison	
		None	
		<i>cmp</i>	
<i>opt_cmp_term</i>	::=	optional result of binary comparison and SMT term	
		None	
		<i>cmp</i> , <i>term</i>	
<i>heap</i> , <i>h</i> , <i>f</i>	::=	heaps	
		{ if <i>term</i> then <i>res</i> ₁ else <i>res</i> ₂ }	
		{ <i>pred</i> & <i>opt_def_heap</i> }	
		{ <i>qpred</i> & <i>arr_def_heap</i> }	
		\overline{heap}_i^i	M
		.	M
		$\sigma(heap)$	M
<i>opt_res_val_heap</i> , <i>opt_def_heap</i>	::=	optional resource term value	
		None	
		<i>def</i> & <i>heap</i>	
		<i>arr_def_heap</i> [<i>term</i>]	
<i>arr_opt_res_val_heap</i> , <i>arr_def_heap</i>	::=	array of optional resource term value	
		.	
		<i>arr_def_heap</i> ₁ + <i>arr_def_heap</i> ₂	
		<i>arr_def_heap</i> [<i>term</i>] := <i>opt_def_heap</i>	
<i>opsem_extra</i>	::=	extra judgements for operational semantics	
		$\forall i < j. \text{not } (pat_i = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma_i)$	
		all patterns prior to <i>j</i> failed to match/deconstruct	

		fresh (<i>mem_ptr</i>) create a fresh address <i>mem_ptr</i>
		<i>term</i> arbitrary logical constraint
<i>misc_extra</i>	::=	extra judgements for proof-related definitions
		$\forall x. \textit{iguard} \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \mathcal{R}$ meta-logical quantification over heap-typing
		$\forall \textit{term} \sim \textit{term}'. \Phi \vdash \textit{fun} \sim \textit{ret}$ meta-logical quantification over related <i>fun</i> and <i>ret</i>
		$\forall \textit{term} \sim \textit{term}'. \Phi \vdash \textit{res} \sim \textit{res}'$ meta-logical quantification over related <i>res</i> and <i>res'</i>
		<i>term</i> \sim <i>term'</i> omitted/assumed defintion: SMT terms <i>term</i> and <i>term'</i> are related
<i>res_judge</i>	::=	
		$\Phi \vdash \text{cmp_min}(\textit{iguard}, \textit{iguard}') \rightsquigarrow \textit{opt_cmp_term}$ given constraints Φ , <i>iguard</i> is potentially included in <i>iguard'</i> (or vice-versa) with ordering and minimum <i>opt_cmp_term</i>
		$\Phi \vdash \textit{qpred_term} \sqsubseteq? \textit{qpred_term}' \rightsquigarrow \textit{opt_cmp}$ given constraints Φ , <i>qpred_term</i> is potentially included in <i>qpred_term'</i> (or vice-versa) with ordering <i>opt_cmp</i>
		$\Phi \vdash \textit{res_req} \equiv \textit{res_req}' \rightsquigarrow \textit{bool}$ resource equality: given constraints Φ , <i>res_req</i> and <i>res_req'</i> are equal according to <i>bool</i>
		$\Phi \vdash \textit{res} \equiv \textit{res}'$ resource equality: given constraints Φ , <i>res</i> is equal to <i>res'</i>
		$\Phi \vdash \text{simp_rec}(\textit{res}) \rightsquigarrow \textit{res}', \textit{bool}$ partial-simplification of resources: given constraints Φ , <i>res</i> partially simplifies (strips ifs) to <i>res'</i>
		$\Phi \vdash \text{simp}(\textit{res}) \rightsquigarrow \textit{opt_res}$ partial-simplification of resources: given constraints Φ , <i>res</i> attempts a partial simplification (strips ifs) to <i>opt_res</i>

ret_judge ::= $\Phi \vdash ret \equiv ret'$
 return type equality: given constraints Φ , ret is equal to ret'

pat_judge ::= $pat:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}$ with $term$
 computational pattern to context: pat and type β produces context \mathcal{C} and constraint $term$

$ident_or_pat:\beta \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}$ with $term$
 identifier-or-pattern to context: $ident_or_pat$ and type β produces context \mathcal{C} and constraint $term$

$\mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash res_pat:res \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
 resources pattern to context: given constraints Φ , res_pat of type res produces contexts $\mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash ret_pat:ret \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
 return pattern to context: given context $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, ret_pat and return type ret produces contexts $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

$\Phi \vdash ret_pat:ret \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
 return pattern to context: given constraints Φ , ret_pat and return type ret produces contexts $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$

$expl_pure$::= $\mathcal{C} \vdash object_value \Rightarrow \beta$
 object value synthesises: given \mathcal{C} , $object_value$ synthesises type β

$\mathcal{C} \vdash pval \Rightarrow \beta$
 pure value synthesises: given \mathcal{C} , $pval$ synthesises type β

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash pexpr \Rightarrow pure_ret$
 pure expression synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, $pexpr$ synthesises a pure (non-resourceful) return type $pure_ret$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash tpval \Leftarrow pure_ret$
 pure top-level value checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, $tpval$ checks against $pure_ret$

		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash tpe\!xpr \Leftarrow pure_ret$ pure top-level expression checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, $tpe\!xpr$ checks against $pure_ret$
$expl_res$::=	
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash pred_ops \Rightarrow res$ resource (q)predicate operation term synthesis: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $pred_ops$ synthesises resource res
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Rightarrow res$ resource term synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, res_term synthesises resource res
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash res_term \Leftarrow res$ resource term checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, res_term checks against resource res
$expl_spine$::=	
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash spine :: fun \gg ret$ function call spine checks: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, compatible $spine$, fun produces an ret
$expl_is_expr$::=	
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash action \Rightarrow ret$ memory action synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $action$ synthesises return type ret
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash memop \Rightarrow ret$ memory operation synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $memop$ synthesises return type ret
		$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_expr \Rightarrow ret$ indet. seq. expression synthesises: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, is_expr synthesises return type ret

$expl_seq_expr ::=$
 | $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_expr \Rightarrow ret$
 seq. expression synthesises: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, seq_expr synthesises
 return type ret

$expl_top ::=$
 | $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash tval \Leftarrow ret$
 top-level value checks: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $tval$ checks against return
 type ret
 | $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow ret$
 top-level seq. expression checks: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, seq_texpr checks
 against return type ret
 | $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow ret$
 top-level indet. seq. expression checks: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, is_texpr
 checks against return type ret
 | $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow ret$
 top-level expression checks: given $C; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, $texpr$ checks against
 return type ret

$inf_res ::=$
 | $\Phi \vdash pred_term \in? qpred_term \rightsquigarrow opt_term$
 given constraints Φ , $pred_term$ is potentially a part of $qpred_term$ at
 index opt_term
 | $\Phi \vdash ident:res \text{ -? } res_req \rightsquigarrow res_diff$
 the difference between $ident:res$ and requested res_req is res_diff
 | $\Phi \vdash ident_1:res \text{ +? } res_term_2:res_req \ \& \ oarg_2 \rightsquigarrow res_term \ \text{and} \ oarg_3$
 combining $ident_1:res$, $res_term_2:res_req \ \& \ oarg_2$, results in res_term
 $oarg_3$
 | $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash wf \ res_req \rightsquigarrow bind \ res_bind \ \text{for} \ res_term \ \text{and} \ oarg \ \dashv \ \underline{\mathcal{R}}'$
 $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ fulfil well-formed request res_req (via res_bind) for answer
 res_term and $oarg$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}}'$ leftover

$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{res_req} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ (check well-formedness of and then) fulfil request res_req (via res_bind) for answer res_term and oarg , with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2 \rightsquigarrow \text{ident} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 under-determined conditional resource request: $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ fulfil request for $\text{if } \text{term} \text{ then } \text{res}_1 \text{ else } \text{res}_2$ with **synthesising** ident and $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

$\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{calc } y \text{ using } \text{res} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{res_term} \text{ and } \text{oarg} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 arbitrary resource and output-arg request: $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ fulfil request for resource res and output-arg y (via res_bind) with **checking** res_term and oarg , leaving resources $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$

$\text{elab_is_expr} ::=$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{action} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{action}' : \text{norm_ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 memory action elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, action elaborates (via res_bind) to $\text{action}' : \text{norm_ret}$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{memop} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{memop}' : \text{norm_ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 memory operation elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, memop elaborates to (via res_bind) to $\text{memop}' : \text{norm_ret}$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{is_expr} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } (\text{is_expr}') : \text{ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 indet. seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, is_expr elaborates (via res_bind) to $\text{is_expr}' : \text{ret}$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

$\text{elab_spine} ::=$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{spine} :: \text{fun} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{spine}' \text{ and } \text{norm_ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 spine elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, arguments spine and function type fun elaborate (via res_bind) to spine' and result type norm_ret , with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

$\text{elab_seq_expr} ::=$

$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash \text{seq_expr} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } \text{res_bind} \text{ for } \text{seq_expr}' : \text{norm_ret} \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
 seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, seq_expr elaborates (via res_bind) to $\text{seq_expr}' : \text{norm_ret}$, with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover

$elab_top ::=$

- | $\Phi \vdash res \rightsquigarrow res_pat$
resource normalisation by pat-matching: under constraints Φ , res will produce a normalised resourced context if it matches against res_pat
- | $\Phi \vdash ret \rightsquigarrow ret_pat$
return-value normalisation by pattern-matching: under constraints Φ , ret will produce a normalised resourced context if it matches against ret_pat
- | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash is_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr$
top-level indet. seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, is_texpr elaborates to $texpr$
- | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash tval \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow \text{bind } res_bind \text{ for } tval' \dashv \underline{\mathcal{R}'}$
top-level value elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, $tval$ elaborates (via res_bind) to $tval'$ with $\underline{\mathcal{R}'}$ leftover
- | $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \rightsquigarrow res_bind$
partial-simplification of resource context: given $\Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$ can partially simplify the resources using res_bind
- | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash seq_texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow seq_texpr'$
top-level seq. expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, seq_texpr checks against \underline{ret} and elaborates to seq_texpr'
- | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}} \vdash texpr \Leftarrow \underline{ret} \rightsquigarrow texpr'$
top-level expression elaboration: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \underline{\mathcal{R}}$, $texpr$ checks against \underline{ret} and elaborates to $texpr'$

$subs_judge ::=$

- | $pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma$
computational value deconstruction: pat deconstructs $pval$ to produce substitution σ
- | $ident_or_pat = pval \rightsquigarrow \sigma$
computational value deconstruction: $ident_or_pat$ deconstructs $pval$ to produce substitution σ

		$\langle h; res_pat = res_val \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle$ resource term deconstruction: res_pat deconstructs res_val to produce substitution σ																				
		$\langle h; \overline{ret_pat_i = ret_term_i^i} \rangle \rightsquigarrow \langle h'; \sigma \rangle$ return value deconstruction: ret_pat_i deconstructs ret_val_i to produce substitution σ																				
		$\langle h; \overline{x_i = spine_elem_i^i} \rangle :: fun \gg \langle h'; \sigma; ret \rangle$ function call spine: heap h and formal parameters x_i assigned to $spine_elem_i$ for function of type fun , produce new heap h' substitution σ and result type ret																				
<i>pure_opsem_defns</i>	::=	<table style="border-collapse: collapse; width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 5%; border-left: 1px solid black; padding-left: 5px;"> </td> <td style="padding-left: 5px;">$\langle pexpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle tpepr: pure_ret \rangle$</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border-left: 1px solid black; padding-left: 5px;"> </td> <td style="padding-left: 5px;">$\langle tpepr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle tpepr' \rangle$</td> </tr> </table>		$\langle pexpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle tpepr: pure_ret \rangle$		$\langle tpepr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle tpepr' \rangle$																
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	$\langle h; texpr \rangle \longrightarrow \langle h'; texpr' \rangle$																					

proof_defns ::=

- | $\overline{x}_i^i :: fun \rightsquigarrow \mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \mid ret$
 matching \overline{x}_i^i and *fun* produces contexts $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$ and return type *ret*
- | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \sqsubseteq \mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
 context weakening: $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$ is stronger than $\mathcal{C}'; \mathcal{L}'; \Phi'; \mathcal{R}'$
- | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R} \vdash \sigma \Leftarrow (\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \mathcal{R})$
 well-typed substitution: given $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi; \mathcal{R}$, σ checks against type $(\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \mathcal{R})$. It is complicated by the fact that substitutions are assumed to be sequential/telescoping.
- | $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 heap typing: under context $\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{L}; \Phi$, heap h checks against context/type $\underline{\mathcal{R}}$
- | $\Phi \vdash h \Leftarrow \underline{\mathcal{R}}$
 heap typing: under context Φ , heap h checks against context/type $\underline{\mathcal{R}}$
- | $\Phi \vdash res \sim res'$
res is related to *res'*
- | $\Phi \vdash fun \sim ret$
fun is related to *ret*

spec_defns ::=

- | $\llbracket spec \rrbracket (opt_ident) = res$
 specification *spec* (with optional record *opt_ident*) represents resource *res* (*opt_ident* is present return when a return is expected, absent when it is not)
- | $\llbracket spec \rrbracket = norm_ret$
 specification *spec* represents normalised return type *norm_ret*
- | $\llbracket spec \mid ret \rrbracket = norm_fun$
 specification *spec* represents normalised argument type *norm_fun*
- | $\llbracket \tau name(\overline{\tau}_i \overline{x}_i^i) \text{ requires } spec_1 \text{ ensures } spec_2 \rrbracket = norm_fun$
 user-defined C function specification represents normalised argument type *norm_fun*

| $\llbracket \text{predicate } \{\overline{\beta_j^i} y_j^j\} \alpha(\overline{\beta_i} x_i^i) \{spec\} \rrbracket = \alpha' \equiv \overline{r_k} : \beta_k''^k \mapsto res$
user-defined resource predicate definition represents predicate